

An underwater photograph of a coral reef. In the foreground, several sea urchins with long, dark spines are visible, resting on a light-colored, porous coral structure. The water is clear and blue, with sunlight filtering through from above, creating a shimmering effect on the surface. The background shows more coral and the water's surface.

Framework for Ecotoxicological Modeling of mCDR (FEMM)

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Executive Summary

Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) encompasses a range of methods that draw down carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere. Alongside widespread greenhouse gas emissions reductions, CDR is regarded as an essential tool for meeting global climate targets. In particular, marine CDR (mCDR) strategies are emerging techniques that harness the ocean to capture and store carbon. Some mCDR strategies, such as Ocean Alkalinity Enhancement (OAE) and Direct Ocean Carbon Capture and Storage (DOCCS) alter seawater carbonate chemistry to allow the ocean to soak up additional CO₂. While these mCDR technologies could offer significant climate mitigation potential, their deployment introduces novel ecological uncertainties that require rigorous, science-based environmental risk assessment (ERA).

The Framework for Ecotoxicological Modeling of mCDR (FEMM) addresses the need for mCDR ERA guidance. FEMM integrates statistical and mechanistic modeling tools into a modular, tiered framework for evaluating ecotoxicological risk and other exposure-mediated risks associated with mCDR projects. It supports both risk screening and advanced risk refinement when needed, thereby adapting to project specifics.

FEMM is intended to support a range of use cases, including project site selection and environmental monitoring design, as well as regulatory decision-making and Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV) environmental impact quantification. By combining established ecotoxicological tools in a flexible, adaptive, and scientifically grounded process, FEMM provides a practical approach to evaluating the ecotoxicological and exposure-mediated risks associated with proposed mCDR projects as well as the impacts of already-implemented projects. FEMM emphasizes flexibility, transparency, and the ability to adapt as new data and project types emerge.

This document introduces:

- Key potential environmental risks of ocean-based climate mitigation approaches such as OAE and DOCC.
- FEMM, a guided approach to assessing ecotoxicological risk and other exposure-mediated risks, such as carbonate chemistry alterations, associated with mCDR projects, including both a screening-level risk assessment framework and refinement approaches to enable advanced risk assessment .
- An overview of species sensitivity distributions (SSDs), a statistical approach to ERA which is recommended for adoption in screening-level mCDR project risk assessment.
- A case study applying the proposed screening-level risk assessment framework to construct a preliminary proof-of-concept SSD for increasing pH using existing datasets.
- A case study demonstrating the utility of region-specific SSDs in refining screening-level risk assessments by constructing general, temperate, and tropical SSDs for nickel toxicity to marine organisms.
- An overview of mechanistic modeling approaches to ERA which are recommended for adoption in advanced mCDR project risk assessment.
- A case study demonstrating the application of mechanistic models to conduct an advanced risk assessment for a sensitive species using monitoring data from a real-world OAE project.
- Recommendations for future work that would meaningfully advance ERA for mCDR projects.

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1. Document Overview

1.1. Document Scope

This document presents the Framework for Ecotoxicological Modeling of mCDR (FEMM). This is a framework for conducting ecotoxicological environmental risk assessment (ERA) of marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) projects that result in changes to seawater chemistry such as the introduction of metals, pesticides or other pollutants, as well as carbonate chemistry perturbations. The framework speaks explicitly to its application for ocean-based climate mitigation approaches such as Ocean Alkalinity Enhancement (OAE) and Direct Ocean Carbon Capture (DOCC), as chemical changes to seawater are typically considered the primary environmental concern for these strategies. However, this framework is also applicable to other current CDR technologies, such as Ocean Iron Fertilization and Terrestrial Biomass Sinking. It is likely that in the future, novel technologies will emerge for which FEMM is also suitable. Because FEMM is structured based on existing risk assessment frameworks for toxicants, FEMM can be immediately applied to stressors such as metals, which are pertinent for mCDR approaches like OAE. This document also identifies opportunities to adapt existing toxicant risk assessment approaches to non-toxicant stressors associated with mCDR (e.g. carbonate chemistry perturbations), which are pertinent for OAE and DOCC approaches. Key aspects of FEMM's approach are exemplified in case studies, using real-world data, throughout the document. This document also identifies next steps and areas where further research is needed to increase the actionability of FEMM. At present, no mCDR-specific regulatory process for environmental risk assessment has been established. As a novel industry with unique environmental and ecotoxicological impacts, a fit-for-purpose approach for assessing environmental impacts is needed. FEMM addresses this need by identifying ERA approaches that can account for the ecotoxicological risks of mCDR and incorporates them into a

tiered, modular system that increases in data requirements and technical complexity only as project risk demands. FEMM provides detailed guidance on how to use and interpret these ERA approaches and ultimately determine whether a proposed mCDR project is likely to be low risk.

This document's primary focus is on established regulatory approaches. In addition, the document identifies modeling tools that, once further developed, could meaningfully improve mCDR ERA and support more comprehensive and complex risk assessment. As such, the framework also proposes an ERA development pathway that emphasizes the generation of datasets suitable for both immediate use in simplified assessments and future integration into more advanced modeling efforts.

Importantly, this framework addresses only ecotoxicological risk and other exposure-mediated risks associated with mCDR. A number of other considerations should be included in a comprehensive environmental risk assessment for mCDR projects; these may include impacts to seawater turbidity levels, noise pollution, or physical disturbance of the seafloor and benthic communities, in addition to impacts associated with the project supply chain. This document is also not a framework for environmental monitoring of mCDR projects, though it is anticipated that efforts to implement this framework will inherently inform field and laboratory data collection. This framework does not provide guidance on best practices for stakeholder engagement with respect to environmental impacts, but rather is likely to serve as an important communication tool for those conducting mCDR engagement programs. Finally, this framework does not present protocols for environmental data standardization and reporting but is best used in conjunction with other frameworks on this topic¹.

1.2. Document Use

This document is intended to guide the development and application of ERA approaches for proposed mCDR projects, in particular for mCDR approaches that

alter seawater chemistry. This framework presents a scientifically grounded structure for determining ecotoxicological and other exposure-mediated risk of mCDR projects in a transparent and adaptive manner. Intended users of this framework are experts and non-experts alike, including researchers, project developers, regulatory reviewers, and standard-setting organizations. This document can be used by:

- researchers or project developers to identify high impact, high priority toxicity testing and model development for mCDR
- project developers to identify low environmental risk project sites and adjust project design such that low project risk can be established
- project developers to identify sensitive species at proposed project sites and, in turn, inform beneficial, additional toxicity testing
- regulatory bodies or any other stakeholder groups that want to better understand the potential environmental risks of an emerging class of marine technologies
- regulatory bodies that seek guidance on best available environmental risk assessment approaches for technologies with novel environmental concerns that existing regulatory guidelines may not adequately address
- standard-setting organizations that would like to incorporate actionable, quantitative environmental impact assessment approaches into Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) protocols, including methodologies for determining safety thresholds and verifying that a project was, or was not, low impact
- standard-setting organizations that would like to use the ERA approaches presented in this framework to guide environmental monitoring and data collection guidelines for mCDR projects

The framework is not a singular, prescriptive workflow for evaluating risk. Instead, it has a modular and adaptable structure, allowing users to tailor assessment components to the specific characteristics of a given technology or project, such as geographic setting, stressor type, and data availability. Distinct risk assessment pathways are available to accommodate varying project designs, but these individual pathways culminate in unified risk assessment criteria, which serve to support consistent and transparent evaluation of environmental risk across the mCDR industry. It offers a shared foundation and standardized set of tools for deriving key threshold values critical to quantitative risk assessment, while remaining responsive to new scientific insights and evolving project needs.

Importantly, this framework is provided for informational purposes only. While care has been taken to ensure the accuracy of the methods and assumptions herein, the author makes no representations or warranties regarding the completeness, reliability, or applicability of this framework to any specific project or context. Any use of this framework is at the user's sole discretion and risk. The author expressly disclaims any liability for direct or indirect damages or consequences resulting from the use, reliance upon, or interpretation of this framework.

Finally, this is a living framework, intended to evolve alongside scientific knowledge, regulatory expectations, and real-world mCDR deployment experience. Users are encouraged to contribute to the refinement of methods through applied case studies and open data practices.

1.3. Document Development

Conceptual development of this framework was led by Grace Andrews of Hourglass Climate. All drafts of the document were prepared by Kristi Weighman (Hourglass Climate) and edited by Emilia Jankowska (Hourglass Climate) and Grace Andrews, with the goal of establishing a clear and actionable framework for risk assessment in the context of mCDR.

An early draft of this document was circulated by invitation for expert review during May and June 2025. Experts were engaged both through targeted outreach and through presentations at two major conferences, the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) Europe 35th Annual Meeting (Vienna) and the Carbon to Sea Initiative 2025 Annual Convening (Washington, D.C.). The review process prioritized engagement with stakeholders from ecotoxicological risk assessment, ocean science, mechanistic modeling, and carbon removal project development. In total, feedback was received from eight reviewers across academia (4), NGOs (1) and industry (3), and originating from 5 countries. Reviewers had the option to remain anonymous or be credited here - Hourglass extends its deep appreciation to: João Barbosa, PhD (Flemish Institute for Biotechnology), Nina Bednaršek, PhD (Oregon State University), Rick Berg, PhD (Banyu Carbon), Tim Cross (Planetary Technologies), Sam Fawcett (PML Applications), Andreas Focks, PhD (University of Osnabrück), Simon Hansul, PhD (University of Osnabrück), and Noemma Olagaray (Cascade Climate). Feedback from this drafting stage informed improvements to technical clarity, methodological consistency, and the inclusion of additional relevant approaches, while also strengthening applicability across diverse use cases. Feedback from this review period was summarized into themes and can be found at hourglassclimate.org/femm “FEMM Draft Expert Review Comment Themes May/June 2025.”

Following the expert review period, a revised draft of FEMM (v0.1) was released for public comment on July 1, 2025 and advertised on the Hourglass Climate website, social media platforms, personal outreach, email listservs, and short presentations at a range of workshops and meetings including the MACAN State-of-the-Science Annual Meeting (Smithsonian Environmental Research Center, MD, USA), the Carbon Business Council July meeting (virtual), and the SEA02-CDR General Assembly (Leiden University, Leiden, Netherlands). The public comment phase was intended to broaden engagement and gather insights from practitioners, researchers, and members of the public with an interest in marine carbon removal, environmental

risk, or ocean governance. The document was downloaded by sixty (60) individuals over the course of the comment period. In total, feedback was received from 13 reviewers across academia (7), industry (5), and government (1) spanning Europe, US, Canada, and Australia. The public comment period subsequently closed on July 31, 2025 although some comments were received after this time and accepted. Public comments were reviewed during Q3 2025 and used to prepare this current revised version, FEMM v1.0, published on February 5, 2026 to hourglassclimate.org. Comments from the public consultation period are provided, anonymously, for traceability and transparency at hourglassclimate.org/femm “FEMM v0.1 Comments July 2025.”

To support transparency and continuous improvement, this document is version-controlled and includes the date of publication. Following major revisions, updates will be reflected in a changelog to document how the framework has evolved in response to feedback and new developments. The latest version of the document, along with its revision history, will be maintained on our website at hourglassclimate.org/femm. Future public comment periods will follow a consistent process, with public notice and an opportunity for stakeholders to provide input. After public consultation periods a summary of feedback will also be published alongside the revised document on our website.

The authors are committed to iterating on this framework as the science, policy, and deployment landscape for mCDR evolves. Future revisions will reflect advances in modeling, monitoring, and empirical understanding, as well as feedback from applied use.

For questions or comments regarding future revisions, contact: femm@hourglassclimate.org

2. Background

Climate change is one of the most significant threats to society and the environment. Numerous scientific publications, such as the IPCC's 6th Assessment Report (AR6), have made clear that to avoid the worst effects of climate change, warming should be held to a 2°C limit by the end of the century. Achieving this goal will require widespread greenhouse gas emission reductions paired with large-scale CDR. CDR technologies include a range of approaches that extract CO₂ from the atmosphere and store it on climate-relevant timescales (i.e. decades to centuries or longer). CDR has a unique role in climate change mitigation, as it represents our only mechanism to address historical greenhouse gas emissions and compensate for hard-to-abate sectors. CDR is thus an integral part of global efforts to limit climate warming².

2.1. Marine Carbon Dioxide Removal

CDR methods vary widely in their mechanisms, scalability, and environmental implications, but ocean-based approaches represent one promising though emerging category. The ocean serves as Earth's largest dynamic carbon reservoir, holding roughly 40 times more carbon than the atmosphere¹. It currently absorbs approximately one-quarter of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions each year, equivalent to billions of tonnes³. Its capacity to store carbon at scale positions it as a possibly significant tool for addressing atmospheric carbon buildup. However, in addition to its role in the global carbon cycle, the ocean is a shared resource, providing food, supporting livelihoods, and holding deep cultural significance around the world. As such, any mCDR interventions must be guided by a rigorous understanding of both effectiveness and potential environmental impacts. This will support informed decision-making by governments, industry, and civil society as interest in mCDR approaches accelerate.

Among the many mCDR strategies, OAE and DOCCS aim to leverage ocean chemistry for long-term CO₂ sequestration⁴. Because seawater chemistry perturbations are the primary environmental concern associated with these technologies, FEMM emphasizes guidance on environmental risk assessment for those two approaches in particular, though it has applicability to other technologies as well.

2.2. Ocean Alkalinity Enhancement

OAE is a CDR strategy that increases the ocean's capacity to capture atmospheric CO₂ by raising seawater alkalinity, its buffering capacity. Two classes of OAE are mineral-based OAE and electrochemical OAE. Mineral-based OAE involves dispersing ground alkaline materials (e.g., olivine, steel slag, brucite, carbonate, lime) into seawater where they dissolve and generate alkalinity. Electrochemical OAE increases alkalinity in water through electrolysis or other chemical processes, and high-alkalinity water is added directly to the ocean. Fundamentally, all OAE techniques perturb the seawater carbonate system. OAE initially increases total alkalinity and pH in seawater, while dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) remains unchanged. These alterations to seawater chemistry are most pronounced immediately at the point of alkalinity addition and as such, this is typically the area of greatest environmental risk. However, mixing with ambient seawater immediately around the project site can decrease the magnitude of the seawater perturbations over short spatial scales. Ultimately, the rise in pH lowers aqueous CO₂ concentrations and in turn, decreases the partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂), creating a gradient that drives seawater uptake of atmospheric CO₂ via air-sea gas exchange. Equilibration with the atmosphere can take years^{5,6} and leaves seawater with elevated alkalinity and DIC relative to baseline conditions while pH returns to near-normal levels, although these changes are effectively imperceptible due to the extensive ambient seawater mixing and dilution that occurs^{7,8}. Additionally, mineral-based OAE can also introduce trace metals and nutrients resulting from mineral feedstock dissolution. In parallel with the carbonate chemistry

perturbations, increases in metal or nutrient concentrations are typically most pronounced at the point of mineral addition but mixing with ambient seawater immediately around the project site can decrease concentrations over short spatial scales.

2.3. Direct Ocean Carbon Capture

DOCC (sometimes referred to as Direct Ocean Removal, or DOR, or more simply Direct Ocean Capture, or DOC) is an approach that extracts CO₂ from seawater in a closed system by altering its pH through electrochemistry. The low-DIC, high-pH seawater is then returned to the ocean. The seawater carbonate chemistry alterations are most significant immediately at the point of discharge and this is considered the area of greatest environmental risk. However, mixing with ambient seawater immediately around the project site can quickly decrease the magnitude of the seawater perturbations. As with OAE, the rise in pH lowers aqueous CO₂ concentrations and in turn, decreases pCO₂, creating a gradient that drives seawater uptake of atmospheric CO₂ via air-sea gas exchange. Equilibration with the atmosphere can take years⁵ but ultimately returns DIC concentrations and pH levels back to background levels⁷. In order for the process to result in CDR, project developers must store the CO₂ that was initially extracted from seawater (e.g. geologic storage); this start-to-finish mCDR approach is called Direct Ocean Carbon Capture and Storage. Alternatively, the captured CO₂ can be used to generate valuable products; in this latter instance, the process is termed Direct Ocean Carbon Capture and Utilization (DOCCU). In either case, the impact on seawater chemistry from DOCC is the same and so DOCC is typically referenced in this document.

2.4. mCDR Technology Development and Commercialization

While the mCDR research and development landscape includes a handful of academic and nonprofit organizations conducting real-world pilots, the field has, to date, been largely driven by commercial actors with the mission to scale carbon

removal projects and with business models based on carbon credit sales. Carbon credit markets require that carbon removal projects demonstrate compliance with Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV) protocols, which ensure credibility and transparency of carbon quantification^{9,10}. MRV methodologies are typically highly detailed and prescriptive as it pertains to carbon removal quantification to ensure rigorous carbon accounting and a trustworthy carbon market. These methodologies also dictate the level of environmental risk assessment and monitoring that a given project must complete to be eligible for credit sales; this is sometimes referred to as “environmental MRV”, or eMRV. However, eMRV protocols are often minimal, qualitative, and presented without structured frameworks for hazard identification, impact threshold quantification, or stepwise assessment. eMRV protocols often place the onus of establishing environmental risk on project developers themselves, creating potential conflicts of interest.

Although it is often assumed that environmental risks will undergo adequate diligence during the permitting process, the current reality is that risks associated with emerging mCDR technologies remain poorly characterized under real-world conditions. Regulatory pathways for mCDR projects are themselves still evolving, and unified assessment criteria create a more level playing field to allow permitting agencies to evaluate applications more efficiently and consistently. The implementation of uniform risk assessment criteria is particularly essential for ensuring the responsible implementation of mCDR projects across jurisdictions with variable standards or where regulatory bodies may lack expertise in novel and rapidly evolving mCDR technologies. In this context, there is a critical need for risk management strategies that evolve alongside scientific knowledge. Any such risks must be weighed transparently against the imperative of climate mitigation and the escalating risks of inaction. Open data sharing and collaborative methodological development will be essential to ensure that environmental risk is not sidelined but treated with the same scientific rigor as carbon accounting itself.

2.5. Alignment with Existing Regulatory Frameworks

As mCDR technologies progress toward scaled deployment, applied ERA frameworks must be not only scientifically robust but also compatible with existing regulatory expectations. FEMM is designed to complement established ERA processes used by regulatory authorities worldwide, offering structured, transparent, and modular tools that can be applied within current legal and permitting contexts.

While specific legal requirements vary by jurisdiction, permitting structures generally share common foundational elements, including hazard identification, exposure characterization, effects characterization, and risk characterization. FEMM is aligned with these core principles and provides practical tools to support their implementation. Its overall structure reflects the architecture of existing regulatory ERA schemes, and its technical components draw directly from a range of guidance documents put forth by international regulatory bodies.

For example, FEMM's use of species sensitivity distributions (SSDs) in risk screening aligns with widely adopted regulatory approaches across the United States, Canada, the European Union, Australia, and New Zealand, where SSDs serve as a standard method for establishing water quality thresholds¹¹⁻¹³. Similarly, the suggested incorporation of mechanistic modeling approaches, such as biotic ligand models (BLMs), reflects their existing use in surface water regulation under tiered metals risk assessment frameworks developed by the U.S. EPA and the European Commission^{14,15}. FEMM also incorporates emerging modeling approaches, such as toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic (TKTD) models, which have begun to be incorporated into regulatory frameworks¹⁶. While the regulatory acceptance of TKTD models is narrower than that of more established approaches, these developing tools are uniquely suited to capture the complex stressor dynamics which are likely to be associated with mCDR deployments. As these methodologies are further standardized and validated, their incorporation will be invaluable for realistic and precautionary ERA in an mCDR context.

Importantly, FEMM is not intended to replace or supersede existing regulatory guidance, but to support informed decision-making within these structures. By aligning its components with the principles embedded in established ERA processes, FEMM provides a foundation that project developers, regulators and verifiers can use to assess mCDR projects in a scientifically credible, precautionary, and regulation-compatible manner.

3. mCDR and Environmental Risk

3.1. Seawater Carbonate Chemistry Perturbations

For both OAE and DOCC, the alteration of carbonate chemistry presents the potential for inducing physiological stress in marine organisms, particularly at or near project sites¹⁷. Both approaches can locally raise seawater pH levels and carbonate mineral saturation states (Ω) and decrease $p\text{CO}_2$. Additionally, OAE can locally increase alkalinity while DOCC releases water low in DIC. Over three decades of ocean acidification (OA) research have shown that calcifying organisms are especially sensitive to disruptions in carbonate chemistry. However, most OA studies have focused on low pH and elevated $p\text{CO}_2$ scenarios, resulting in limited knowledge about biological responses under the conditions relevant to mCDR technologies. The environmental risks associated with carbonate chemistry perturbations from OAE and DOCC projects are dependent on the project size and design (e.g. amount of material, discharge volume, discharge rate), rate of mixing with ambient seawater, and the duration of the period between the release and equilibration with the atmosphere^{7,17}. When changes in carbonate chemistry exceed the natural variability of marine systems, they create novel conditions that may particularly affect species lacking acclimatization strategies⁸.

Exposure to elevated pH and alkalinity can affect marine organisms by disrupting acid-base regulation, metabolism, calcification, and other physiological processes.

Studies have reported reduced growth and survival in juvenile razor clams¹⁸ and physiological impairments in species such as crabs¹⁹, sea slugs²⁰, and fish²¹⁻²⁴ when exposed to high-pH conditions. These effects are often most pronounced during early developmental stages¹⁸. Bacterial metabolism depends on pH homeostasis, and even small pH shifts can alter marine bacterial communities²⁵. Research on the effects of ocean liming on copepods found that short-term exposure (<6 h) to pH 9 caused no adverse effects, whereas 24h exposure to pH >9 led to increased mortality and sublethal impacts²⁶. Bednarsek et al. (2025) compiled results from multiple OA and OAE studies and predicted that more than 60% of marine calcifying species exhibited non-neutral (either positive or negative) responses to enhanced alkalinity, highlighting variable sensitivity among taxa⁸. Low DIC and increased carbonate saturation states can influence key physiological processes in marine organisms. Under low DIC conditions, photosynthesis, calcification, and acid-base regulation may be impaired¹⁷. Laboratory studies have shown that photosynthetic organisms such as phytoplankton and macroalgae become carbon-limited when DIC concentrations are low. Phytoplankton rely on DIC for photosynthesis, and low dissolved CO₂ concentrations can limit primary productivity^{27,28}. Although most phytoplankton use carbon-concentrating mechanisms to cope with low CO₂, their efficiency varies among taxa²⁹. These effects may be further intensified by elevated pH, which lowers the relative availability of CO₂ and bicarbonate ions (HCO₃⁻), potentially compounding the limitation of total DIC. At the same time, increased carbonate saturation states alter the balance among calcium ions (Ca²⁺), carbonate ions (CO₃²⁻), and calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), potentially affecting biological calcification and other physiological processes. Reduced calcification rates can occur in marine macroalgae and bivalves³⁰.

Increased alkalinity and pH may also initially benefit calcifying organisms, such as corals, coccolithophores, and shell-forming mollusks by increasing carbonate ion availability and enhancing calcification rates^{31,32}. However, the long-term ecological effect on local populations remains uncertain. Elevated alkalinity may not benefit all

taxa equally; certain planktonic or calcifying groups could gain a competitive advantage, while others may experience physiological stress or reduced growth under altered carbonate conditions. Such differential responses have the potential to disrupt community structure and ecosystem balance by favoring some species over others^{33,34}.

The carbonate chemistry parameter that most strongly influences physiological processes is likely to vary among taxa. Some organisms are primarily affected by elevated pH or reduced $p\text{CO}_2$ ¹⁹, while others are more sensitive to decreases in DIC or shifts in calcium ion balance³⁵. Beyond impacts on individual species, differing sensitivities across taxa, particularly the potential advantages for calcifying organisms, raise concerns about altered species interactions and ecosystem balance in environments affected by mCDR³⁶. Such changes in carbonate chemistry could shift competitive dynamics and modify community composition^{30,37,38}. Because carbonate parameters are interdependent, the physiological stresses they impose may act together, compounding their effects. Similarly to traditional toxicant stress, these impacts are also likely to be influenced by environmental factors such as temperature and food availability.

The complex sensitivity of different species to changes in carbonate chemistry underscores the need for further assessment and research on potential stressors related to OAE and DOCC. Assessment should include a wide range of species, particularly non-calcifiers, which remain underrepresented in current research and include realistic exposures to OAE and DOCC derived stressors. Understanding how carbonate system changes affect marine species and community dynamics is essential for assessing whether these outcomes may pose ecological risks across a range of mCDR approaches.

3.2. Dissolution Products of Mineral-based OAE

Mineral-based OAE involves the addition and dissolution of alkaline materials such as olivine, steel slag, brucite, and lime, each releasing a distinct suite of trace elements into the marine environment^{39,40}. Potential dissolution products include, but are not limited to, silica (Si), iron (Fe), magnesium (Mg), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co) vanadium (V), and selenium (Se), depending on the feedstock^{41,42}(Appendix A). Some of these elements may provide ecological benefits; for instance, Si and Fe can enhance primary productivity by stimulating diatom growth in regions where these nutrients are limiting³⁶. Others, however, may pose toxicity risks to marine organisms at elevated concentrations^{32,40}.

Although certain trace metals, such as copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), Ni, and lead (Pb), have been relatively well studied in marine ecotoxicology, many of the additional elements released by OAE feedstocks, such as Cr and Co, remain less thoroughly characterized. Their effects on marine species are likely to vary depending on biological sensitivity, bioavailability, and local seawater chemistry. For example, metal toxicity can be strongly modulated by pH, complexation with other ions, and the presence of dissolved organic carbon^{43,44}. Ni, as one illustrative case, has been shown to disrupt metabolic function and ion regulation in sensitive species, but risks depend heavily on exposure context⁴⁵.

Ultimately, the influence of dissolution products associated with mineral-based OAE can be positive, negative, or neutral for climate change-stressed ecosystems³². Given the diversity of potential inputs and the limited ecotoxicological data available for many elements, broad assumptions about ecological safety are inappropriate. Instead, mineral-specific characterization and site-based environmental risk assessment will be essential to evaluating OAE deployments. These assessments should incorporate both well-understood and data-deficient substances, using a combination of laboratory testing, statistical methods, predictive modeling and monitoring to account for acute and chronic exposures.

3.3. Addition Mechanisms of Potential Environmental Risk

The framework presented in this document is designed to allow for the risk assessment of ecotoxicological risk and other exposure-mediated risks associated with mCDR projects during and subsequent to project deployment. Additionally, a variety of non-toxicological mechanisms of environmental risk may be presented by mCDR projects⁴⁶. Disturbances associated with deployment processes, such as noise pollution from boats, may incur unintended effects on marine life. Following deployments, resultant turbidity may have consequences for organism behavior, photosynthetic processes, and predator/prey dynamics⁴⁷. For mineral-based OAE, the shape, size and color of feedstocks that settle on the seafloor may alter sediment composition and have mechanical implications for behaviors such as burrowing and avoidance^{48,49}. Dilution of dissolved organic carbon in sediment may also result in reduced feeding efficacy for some organisms. Additionally, there are supply-chain processes required to implement projects or manage project-related waste that also warrant consideration in holistic evaluation of the environmental risks associated with mCDR⁵⁰. While supply-chain, waste management, and non-exposure-mediated environmental effects are not considered in FEMM, these effects very plausibly present risk, and should be considered as ERA of mCDR projects continues to be developed.

3.4. Key Takeaways: mCDR and Ecotoxicological Risk

- 1** Environmental risks from mCDR are both site-specific and approach-dependent.
- 2** OAE and DOCC cause local changes to seawater carbonate chemistry which may hinder or support organisms' survival and growth as well as impact physiological processes such as calcification.
- 3** Mineral-based OAE can release trace elements and nutrients into seawater, with the potential to enhance productivity or cause toxicity, depending on local context.
- 4** Potential environmental risk associated with supply chain processes, waste management processes, and non-toxicological stressors associated with mCDR warrant serious consideration, but fall outside the scope of FEMM.

4. FEMM Overview

The Framework for Ecotoxicological Modeling of mCDR (FEMM) builds on established environmental risk assessment (ERA) methodologies, particularly species sensitivity distributions (SSDs) and mechanistic modeling, which are widely used in regulatory and research contexts. FEMM combines these statistical and mechanistic components to provide an integrated, tiered, flexible approach to risk assessment (Figure 1). SSDs are a statistically robust foundation for screening-level risk assessment, offering concise summary metrics derived from standardized laboratory data with relatively low analytical complexity (Section 6). Mechanistic models are a powerful complement by simulating how stressors disperse, transform, and affect organisms under dynamic environmental conditions. These tools can incorporate site-specific parameters, biological traits, and exposure variability to produce more realistic, predictive outcomes (Section 7).

FEMM first guides project assessors through an SSD-based risk screening process (Figure 7) to quantify key metrics, namely Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PECs) and Predicted No-Effect Concentrations (PNECs). A comparison of PEC and PNEC values provides an initial determination of project risk. Where advanced assessment is recommended, FEMM next provides guidance on mechanistic modeling pathways (Figure 12) that can refine predictions of exposure (Section 7.2) and biological effects (Section 7.3). Improved PEC and/or PNEC estimates generate a refined risk determination. The same framework can be used to conduct post-deployment impact assessments using Measured Environmental Concentrations (MECs) in place of PECs.

By design, FEMM moves from simple to complex approaches and, where steps along the FEMM pathway are today not readily implementable due to the emerging nature of the mCDR field, FEMM offers suggestions for conservative interim measures and directions for future work. Ultimately, adoption and adaptation of the ERA methods

detailed in FEMM to the unique challenges of mCDR will accelerate the development of scientifically grounded, standardized ERA, ensuring that potential mCDR project risks are rigorously characterized and responsibly managed.

Figure 1. Summary of the FEMM pathway

Project risk assessment begins with screening-level assessment based on statistical approaches. Screening outputs, specifically the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC) and the Predicted No-Effect Concentration (PNEC) are used to assess risk. Where potential risk is indicated, an advanced risk assessment can be conducted using mechanistic models to refine PEC and PNEC estimates. The same pathway can be followed to conduct post-deployment impact assessments using the Measured Environmental Concentration (MEC) instead of the PEC. Detailed screening risk assessment and advanced risk assessment schematics can be found in Figure 7 and Figure 12, respectively.

5. Exposure Assessment

The stressors associated with a given mCDR project vary with methodology and materials. These potential stressors can include both toxicants, such as metals, for which regulatory guidance is more likely to exist, and other non-toxicant stressors, such as carbonate chemistry perturbations, for which regulatory guidance is more limited (Appendix A). FEMM follows established frameworks based on ERA of toxicants and proposes the adaptation of the same assessment frameworks for non-toxicant stressors. For any stressor, ERA for a proposed project relies on understanding environmental exposure and estimating a predicted environmental concentration (PEC). Exposure assessment describes how the stressor travels from its source to organisms and the relevant route of exposure, such as ambient water exposure or ingestion⁵¹⁻⁵³. Exposure can be characterized as a single time-averaged PEC, as is used in FEMM screening risk assessment (Section 6), or as a time-variable PEC profile, which can be used in more advanced risk assessment^{51,52}. Potential environmental stress is expected to increase as the PEC increases. In the case of carbonate chemistry perturbations, potential stress may not always be most appropriately described as a function of stressor “concentration”, as is typical for toxicants. However, the PEC concept can still be applied to describe how stress is expected to increase with the magnitude of disruption from baseline. PEC values can be established to estimate potential exposure for any number of stressors associated with a project, with stressors being characterized as individual components or as whole-mixtures (Section 6.5). Once value(s) are established for a project, the potential for risk associated with that exposure can be assessed for stressors individually or in combination.

The first step in ERA is to identify the stressor for which risk is being assessed⁵². Depending on the mCDR technology, this may be required for one or more of the aforementioned stressors, such individual metals, particular carbonate chemistry parameters, or a combination of stressors where a whole-mixture approach is used

(Appendix A, Section 6.5). Project planners should then identify the environmental compartment within the project site where stressor concentrations are likely to be the highest. Environmental compartments within the project site, such as the water column, porewater, and sediment, will differ in their exposure dynamics, resulting in different compartment PECs⁵¹. Because the influence of dilution will be minimal at the point of stressor input into the environment, the compartment associated with the point of input will likely have the highest potential stress. For example, high-risk compartments may be in the water column at or near the mouth of a discharge pipe for mCDR strategies that use wastewater treatment or desalinization plants to discharge feedstock or the sediment and/or porewater for mineral feedstocks that settle on the seafloor before complete dissolution occurs.

After identifying high-risk compartment(s), an estimate of the maximum plausible stressor concentration within that compartment must be established⁵¹. This estimate can incorporate factors dependent on both project-design, such as release rate, and project site, such as residence time. These project-specific factors inform the spatial and temporal scales over which the maximum plausible stressor concentration within the compartment should be estimated^{51,52}. When identifying likely high-risk compartments and estimating maximum plausible stressor concentrations, underlying assumptions should default towards conservatism and be clearly documented.

In addition to the amount of stressor being introduced by the project itself, other considerations regarding how it will interact with the environment should be incorporated. Background concentrations or inputs of the stressor from other sources should be added to proposed project inputs to estimate the total PEC. Although, in some cases, organisms may acclimatize to relatively high background stressor concentrations, acclimation cannot be safely assumed. An additive approach to PEC establishment is most conservative and wards against further stressing already stressed ecosystems^{52,53}.

Once a PEC has been established, it should be compared with relevant regulatory guidance whenever possible. The outcome of the risk assessment pathway presented in FEMM should never be interpreted as superseding regulatory criteria, and any predicted exceedance of relevant regulation necessitates project redesign. If no regulatory criteria are in place, project planners may benefit from seeking out relevant guidance that has been established in other jurisdictions. Although sensitivity may be regionally variable, established criteria outside the jurisdiction of the project site can serve as a useful guidepost to help project planners infer whether their PEC is plausibly low-risk before proceeding through the risk assessment pathway.

In keeping with the principle of conservatism, the PEC for the highest-risk compartment should be treated as the project PEC and used to assess risk at the community level, which is intended to preserve ecosystem integrity in the entirety of the project site. However, multiple PECs may be established to reflect differing exposure between environmental compartments. For example, a project could establish a PEC_{sediment} , $PEC_{\text{watercolumn}}$, and $PEC_{\text{porewater}}$. Establishing PECs for compartments that are not considered the highest risk may be worthwhile if, for example, those compartments are most relevant for species of special concern. Such species may include hyper-sensitive species or species of economic or cultural importance. A more relevant compartment PEC can be validly used to assess species-specific risk as long as low risk is first established at the community level using the highest-risk compartment PEC. This approach offers the opportunity for species-specific refinement without necessitating more complex mechanistic modeling.

While a compartment-based approach may allow for species-specific risk assessment without the need for more effort-intensive mechanistic modeling, advanced exposure assessment may also incorporate factors such as bioavailability, bioaccumulation, and biomagnification (Section 7). These dynamics are often taxa-specific and contingent on life-history and allometric traits and will generally be

most relevant to species-specific assessments. A number of statistical and mechanistic approaches are available to refine PEC estimates by incorporating these processes^{52,54} (Figure 12).

In addition to their utility in risk assessment, PECs should be used to inform proactive decision-making in both deployment design and monitoring strategy. Decisions regarding deployment location within the project site, as well as magnitude and intervals of deployments, can be made to minimize the magnitude of disruption to compartments within the project site. Following the structured risk assessment pathway can help to focus monitoring efforts by identifying high-risk compartments and creating clear points of comparison between pre-deployment predictions and post-deployment measurements.

Post-deployment monitoring can produce Measured Environmental Concentrations (MECs). If the FEMM risk pathway has been used to establish low project risk pre-deployment, MECs that remain at or below the corresponding PECs are consistent with a low risk of environmental impact. Where a MEC exceeds the corresponding PEC, or in cases where the pathway was not used to assess potential risk pre-deployment, the pathway can be used to establish low environmental impact by using MECs in place of PECs. Structured risk and impact assessment can enable early detection of cases where actual risk exceeds predicted risk by providing clear points of comparison. Early detection increases the opportunity for remediation efforts or adjusting dosing/dispersal methods for ongoing deployments. When PEC establishment and monitoring design are aligned, the comparison of PECs and MECs can also be useful in validating assumptions that underlie exposure predictions, such as estimated rates of dissolution or dilution, and identifying where those assumptions may not be adequately protective⁵¹.

5.1. Key Takeaways: Exposure Assessment

1 Assessing project-level risk relies on establishing predicted environmental concentration(s) (PECs) that characterize the magnitude of stressor exposure under a plausible worst-case-scenario.

2 Exposure profiles may differ across environmental compartments within a project site, such as the water column, porewater, and sediment. To ensure conservative risk assessment, the PEC for the highest-risk compartment should be used for community-level risk assessment.

3 Deriving PECs for multiple compartments, including relatively low-risk compartments, may be useful in species-specific risk assessment.

4 Post-deployment impact assessments can be conducted by replacing PECs with measured environmental concentrations (MECs) in the risk assessment framework.

6. Screening-Level Risk Assessment

Screening-level risk assessment in FEMM is based on the adaptation of statistical approaches, which are well-established in ERA for toxicants. These statistical approaches allow for the establishment of a Predicted No-Effect Concentration (PNEC). The PNEC is the estimated stressor concentration at which no effect is predicted at the community-level and is compared to the PEC (Section 5) to assess potential project risk. Following screening-level risk assessment, advanced risk assessment offers opportunities for refinement of both PEC and PNEC values, if needed (Section 7).

6.1. Species Sensitivity Distributions

SSDs are commonly used in ERA to predict the percentage of species in an ecosystem that may be affected by different concentrations of a stressor. Chronic SSDs are routinely applied to derive environmental quality standards (EQS) under regulatory frameworks such as those of the US EPA, CCME, ECHA, and the European Commission^{12,15,55,56}.

SSDs are constructed from species-specific toxicity data, which are compiled to describe the range of observed sensitivity to a stressor across taxa. The sensitivity of each species within an SSD is determined via toxicity testing. Effect concentration (EC_x) values for the species are estimated by fitting a dose-response curve (DRC) to experimental observations. An effect concentration is the concentration estimated to result in a percent (x) effect on sublethal biological endpoints, such as growth or reproduction, for a given species. As an example, an EC₁₀ is the concentration that is anticipated to cause a 10% effect on a specific endpoint for the species. SSDs may also incorporate lethal effect concentrations (LC_x), which is the concentration estimated to result in a percent (x) mortality for a given species. However, LC_x values are most commonly derived from acute toxicity tests, which rely on short exposure

durations and generally include relatively high test concentrations. As such, LCx values are typically included in acute SSDs. To maintain conservatism, chronic SSDs, which typically rely on sublethal ECx values derived from chronic exposure tests, are preferred in ERA unless exposure is expected to be exclusively short-term. Due to the prolonged exposure periods anticipated for many stressors associated with mCDR projects (Section 2), the SSD-based risk assessment described in this document should default to the use of chronic SSDs unless exposure can be demonstrated to be exclusively acute. If chronic toxicity test data are unavailable, acute data may be extrapolated for inclusion in chronic SSDs, but any such extrapolation necessitates accounting for associated uncertainty (Section 6.4).

To derive a chronic SSD, a cumulative distribution function is fit to ECx values. This distribution is intended to approximate the range of sensitivities across taxa, not only the sensitivities of the included species. As such, the construction of a reliable SSD requires adequate taxonomic breadth to be considered representative. Criteria for the use of SSDs in establishing EQS vary across regulatory bodies, but generally dictate the inclusion of a minimum of 10 species spanning 8 base taxonomic groups¹². Further information regarding taxonomic diversity requirements and recommended taxa for toxicity testing relevant to mCDR can be found in Appendix B. SSDs can be established to describe sensitivity to either dissolved or solid-phase exposures, provided sufficient experimental data are available for the relevant exposure route.

SSDs are used to derive the Hazard Concentration for 5% of species (HC5), a key regulatory endpoint which approximates the concentration at which 5% of species are predicted to be affected. HC5 values provide a statistical basis for deriving reference values for environmental safety. They are typically adjusted using an Assessment Factor (AF), or a comparable uncertainty factor, depending on the regulatory framework. Assessment factors are applied to account for uncertainty and to ensure that thresholds derived from HC5s, such as EQS values, are protective¹². A smaller AF is appropriate when the SSD is based on high-quality, taxonomically

representative chronic toxicity data, while a larger AF is used when there are greater uncertainties, limited species coverage, or extrapolated endpoints (Section 6.4). Typically, in an SSD approach, an AF is applied to derive a Predicted No-Effect Concentration (PNEC). The PNEC is derived from an SSD by dividing the HC5 by the appropriate AF. Once a PNEC has been established, this standard is compared to measured or predicted environmental concentrations (MEC or PEC) to assess whether a chemical concentration poses a risk to the environment⁵⁷. RQs may also be refined to better approximate risk in particular compartments, provided a relevant SSD has been established. For example, an SSD based on dissolved-phase exposure data may be compared to a $PEC_{\text{watercolumn}}$ and $PEC_{\text{porewater}}$ to approximate the RQs for pelagic and benthic communities, respectively. Alternatively, an SSD based on solid-phase exposure may also be compared to the PEC_{sediment} to refine the RQ for benthic communities. While these refinements are contingent on adequate data availability, it is recommended that project planners utilize the most protective relevant risk assessment criteria (resulting in the highest RQ) wherever possible. For species-specific risk assessment, the most species-relevant compartment PEC may be compared to the species ECx to assess risk for a species of special concern, rather than the ecosystem as a whole. In some cases, more stringent RQ criteria may also be appropriate. For example, the US EPA Office of Pesticide Program uses a threshold of $RQ \geq 0.05$ to flag potential acute risk to endangered species⁵⁴.

Because SSDs represent the distribution of individual-species sensitivity data within a species assemblage (as a proxy for the biological community), they can be used to rank the most sensitive endpoints between species. Species that appear on the lower tail of the SSD are considered more sensitive and may serve as candidates for bioindicator species, depending on their ecological relevance and the feasibility of monitoring. In the context of mCDR project planning, these species may warrant more detailed risk assessment, particularly if they exhibit sensitivity at or below the PEC. When related species, or species sharing key biological traits (e.g., mode of calcification), are closely placed along the distribution, it may indicate consistent

sensitivity patterns within that group and could be used to help identify particularly sensitive taxa for prioritization in research or monitoring.

6.2. SSDs for mCDR

To date, chronic marine SSDs have only been developed for a handful of metals, namely Ni, Co, and Pb⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. For other metals such as Cu, As, and Cd, chronic marine SSDs exist but are less complete and often rely on extrapolation methods, which introduce additional uncertainty^{14,61} (Section 6.4). The experimental generation of high-quality chronic marine toxicity data for mCDR-relevant metals across diverse taxa (Appendix A, Appendix B) is essential for constructing rigorous and fit-for-purpose SSDs that serve mCDR ERA. As previously noted, regulatory guidelines emphasize the inclusion of a core set of taxa to represent key ecological groups and trophic levels. These include primary producers such as diatoms and aquatic plants, primary consumers such as copepods and amphipods, and fish. In the context of mCDR risk assessment, including species sensitive to changes in carbonate chemistry, such as calcifiers, and those important for ecosystem recovery, such as early colonizers, is ideal to ensure SSD-derived endpoints are adequately protective (Appendix B). Although regulatory criteria for base taxa, which have largely been established for freshwater risk assessments, may not be directly transferable to marine environments⁵⁸, marine SSDs should follow established data quality criteria as closely as possible. Accordingly, SSDs for mCDR should include at least 10 species spanning 8 taxonomic groups¹², although the taxonomic groups represented may be adapted to better reflect the relevant marine ecosystems.

No SSD-based framework has been applied to derive safe thresholds for carbonate chemistry parameters in relation to mCDR. However, an SSD approach has been utilized to evaluate relative sensitivities of marine taxa to OA using pCO₂ as the stressor⁶². SSDs have also been successfully used to assess sensitivity to nonchemical stressors like temperature and salinity⁶³. OAE and DOCC alter multiple, interrelated components of the carbonate system, including pH and carbonate

mineral saturation states, and applying an SSD approach to carbonate chemistry perturbations presents several conceptual and practical challenges. Each parameter may induce stress through distinct physiological mechanisms. If a particular parameter can be identified as the dominant driver of biological effects, a standard SSD approach may be applied for this stressor. However, if multiple carbonate chemistry parameters meaningfully contribute to observed effects, their interdependence complicates the derivation of conventional DRCs (species-level) and SSDs (community level). Proxies and summary statistics may help to simplify the complex, interdependent nature of carbonate chemistry stressors, with TA:DIC ratio having been identified as a useful proxy in characterizing biological responses to OAE in marine calcifiers⁸. In addition to the challenge of parameter interdependence, as in the establishment of PECs (Section 5), the application of an SSD framework to carbonate chemistry parameters is complicated by the absence of a clear concentration or “dose”, which can be treated as a no-exposure condition. Defining this control condition as well as defining how exposure “dose” is defined relative to that condition, is a key element in applying statistical models to describe the exposure-response relationship. Further research will be required to determine whether, for individual carbonate chemistry parameters, stressor-response relationships are best described as a function of absolute parameter values or as a function of the change in value from baseline environmental conditions.

Beyond uncertainty surrounding the identification of key stressors and how “dose” of those stressors can be best quantified, the adaptation of ecotoxicological frameworks to assess risk related carbonate chemistry perturbations also requires evaluation of the model distributions that underlie traditional dose-response analysis. In ecotoxicology, dose-response relationships have typically been described using monotonic sigmoidal distributions. The appropriateness of these distributions in describing carbonate chemistry perturbations warrants further scrutiny. If observed response data cannot be well-described using standard ecotoxicological approaches, the consideration of alternative modeling paradigms may be required⁶⁴.

Although some species exhibit positive responses to carbonate chemistry perturbations, such as an upward shift in pH, it cannot be safely assumed that larger upward shifts in pH would continue to result in positive responses. For example, if the ideal pH range for the observed species is below baseline environmental conditions, an upward shift in pH of a certain magnitude may result in a positive response. However, an upward pH shift of a greater magnitude may result in a negative response. Previous analyses of OA and OAE studies indicate that a range of taxa exhibit non-monotonic responses to carbonate chemistry shifts^{8,65}. In ecotoxicology, analogous non-monotonic stressor-response profiles have been observed for essential trace metals and for some pharmacologically active substances^{66,67}. For these stressors, low doses result in a positive biological response, but higher doses result in a negative response^{66,68}. When the positive responses observed at low doses are deemed sufficiently large as to be relevant to risk assessment, these non-monotonic dose-response relationships have been addressed using hormesis models⁶⁹. Hormesis models define an “optimum” stressor value, and stress on biological functions is expected to increase as the stressor value deviates from the optimum in either direction, resulting in a “u”-shaped DRC⁶⁶. Hormesis models may therefore be useful in defining stressor-response relationships in cases where more established monotonic DRCs cannot adequately describe observed responses to carbonate chemistry perturbations.

The adaptation of both monotonic and non-monotonic stressor-response models could provide a tractable pathway towards establishing ECx values for carbonate chemistry perturbations, which are required for the construction of SSDs. The application of these ecotoxicological assessment tools to carbonate chemistry perturbations presents many challenges, including the identification of the most important stressors as well as the most appropriate “dose” metrics and model distributions. Clarifying best-practices under these frameworks will require standardized, high-quality toxicity datasets that span environmentally relevant parameter ranges and diverse marine taxa. Consistent measurement and reporting of

the suite of carbonate system parameters, alongside adherence to OECD test guidelines where applicable, will improve comparability and support the development of robust, transferable assessment frameworks. Ultimately, these efforts will also lay the groundwork for mechanistic modeling approaches, which may be better suited to capturing the internal physiological processes and tipping points associated with carbonate chemistry stress.

6.2.1. Case Study 1: A Proof-of-Concept pH SSD

To explore the feasibility of adapting ecotoxicological risk assessment approaches to the carbonate chemistry perturbations associated with some mCDR strategies (Section 6.2), a preliminary SSD was developed that approximates a sensitivity distribution for increased seawater pH.

The data were compiled from several multi-species synthesis publications, which included both OA and OAE studies^{8,62,70}. These sources aggregate response datasets across diverse taxa. Only species that exhibited negative effects in higher-pH treatments were included in the present analysis. Species without observed negative effects were excluded since this analysis is only intended to examine whether an SSD approach is workable for mCDR project risk assessment, where alkalinization, not acidification, is most relevant. However, because OA studies were included, “higher” pH conditions were defined between in-study treatments, and do not necessarily represent an increase in pH from seawater pH values typically found in natural environments. This limitation is further discussed throughout this case study.

Figure 2. Example DRC for increasing pH

A log-logistic dose-response curve (DRC) was fitted to observed growth rate data for the diatom *Thalassionema nitzschioides* across experimental pH treatments. $\Delta pH = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

Figure 3. Proof-of-concept SSD for increasing pH

Each species' EC10 value corresponds to the within-study increase in pH that reduced growth or calcification by 10%, relative to the pH treatment where the highest response was reported for that endpoint. EC10 values are not assumed to represent equal distances from natural environmental pH baselines or true species optima. This species sensitivity distribution (SSD) is exploratory only and not suitable for risk assessment at this stage. It is intended solely as a demonstration that parametric distributions commonly applied in toxicant SSD fitting may also be applicable to carbonate chemistry stress responses.

The adaptation of tools, such as DRCs and SSDs, shows promise for developing an ERA framework for mCDR carbonate chemistry perturbations that aligns with established regulatory methods for toxicants. Monotonic stressor-response data could be fitted with the same statistical models commonly used in ecotoxicology. In our preliminary exploration, log-logistic DRCs were fitted to individual species' ΔpH response profiles to establish species' EC10 estimates. Similarly, traditional parametric models could be reasonably fitted to those EC10s to construct an SSD for responses to ΔpH .

However, this approach is not currently suitable for use in applied risk assessment and will require further development. Many limitations arise from the sparse data available for reliable model-fitting. To reduce over-extrapolation in the proof-of-concept SSD, only species with EC10 estimates that fell inside the experimentally observed pH range of the original studies were included in the SSD. However, response data for some species did not contain an adequate range of observed decreases in growth/calcification (relative to optimum) to support reliable DRC fitting. These species' EC10 estimates were still included in the SSD to improve taxonomic coverage, but these must be considered as exploratory only (Appendix C). Despite this, the assembled dataset still does not cover a sufficiently wide range of taxa to be considered ecologically representative (Section 6.1). Furthermore, much of the response data originated from OA experiments. In those studies, some species showed improved growth or calcification when pH was reduced, meaning that some of the negative responses retained for SSD fitting here were based on within-study contrasts, not an upward shift from natural baseline pH. While it is plausible that these species would respond negatively to alkalinization relative to their environmental baselines, the dataset used here does not fully represent the carbonate chemistry perturbations expected from mCDR deployments. Because OA studies focus on lower pH ranges, the current dataset is likely biased toward species that are unusually sensitive to increasing pH. Combined with limited taxonomic breadth, these gaps would make any derived hazard threshold unreliable. For this reason, no HC5 or other risk screening benchmark was calculated from this preliminary SSD.

Building on this proof-of-concept will require overcoming fundamental data gaps and further evaluating model-fitting methodologies. The current dataset should be systematically expanded as new data become available, including targeted experiments for core taxonomic groups that remain unrepresented due to a lack of published response data for alkalinity enhancement (Appendix B). This will require both further technical development and independent peer review before it can be

considered for applied risk assessment. Nevertheless, SSD demonstrates potential as a pathway for treating carbonate chemistry perturbations as a quantifiable ecological stressor by building on existing regulatory frameworks.

6.3. Context-Specific SSDs

SSDs are valuable for capturing broad patterns of species sensitivity across diverse taxa and environments. To enable broad taxonomic inclusion, SSDs are typically constructed incorporating species from a wide variety of regions, often with SSDs being constructed for marine or freshwater species, irrespective of region. This approach can be beneficial, as the inclusion of additional taxa will improve the distribution so long as there are no region-specific discrepancies in sensitivity. However, where adequate data is available, constructing SSDs for specific regions or taxonomic groups can yield more context-specific insights for assessing ecological risks associated with a particular mCDR project. For instance, species in a given region may exhibit distinct sensitivities to stressors due to physiological and ecological adaptations, making more general SSDs less reflective of true local vulnerability⁷¹⁻⁷³. Several studies have examined whether species sensitivity to various chemicals differs regionally. While sensitivity to a given chemical is generally consistent across regions, notable exceptions have been identified^{63,74-77}. In cases where variation in regional sensitivity is plausible, region-specific SSDs that incorporate local species can provide more accurate hazardous concentration thresholds (e.g., HC5) and offer better protection for local biodiversity.

SSDs focusing on the most likely affected organism groups may also be appropriate in specific risk assessments^{78,79}. The rationale for constructing SSDs based exclusively on sensitive species is that HC5s, or other safety thresholds, derived from broader species pools may not be protective for these more vulnerable groups. For example, aquatic arthropods such as crustaceans and aquatic insects are known to be particularly sensitive to pesticides⁶³. To account for such taxonomic differences in sensitivity, the development of separate SSDs is already being considered in

insecticide risk assessment^{78,80}. Similarly, in the context of mCDR, taxa particularly vulnerable to changes in carbonate chemistry, such as calcifiers, may warrant dedicated SSDs.

While context-specific SSDs may improve the relevance of SSD-derived safety thresholds for particular regions, environmental compartments, or sensitive taxa, this benefit must be weighed against the disadvantage of narrower data availability. Stricter inclusion criteria, such as regional specificity or a focus on sensitive taxa, inherently result in a smaller dataset for SSD-fitting, which may increase statistical uncertainty around derived thresholds. Stricter selection criteria may also reduce taxonomic breadth, limiting ecological representativeness. Broad taxonomic representation is essential for constructing reliable SSDs, and context-specific SSDs should be held to the same standards of taxonomic breadth as is recommended for more general SSDs (Appendix B), except in cases where SSDs are intentionally limited to specific taxonomic groups.

6.3.1. Case Study 2: Comparison of General vs. Region-Specific SSDs

As many candidate OAE feedstocks such as olivine, brucite, and steel slag dissolve in seawater to enhance alkalinity and promote CO₂ uptake, they also release trace elements, notably Ni. The release of Ni and other trace elements into marine habitats creates potential environmental risk, necessitating structured assessment. SSDs have long been used to assess the environmental risk associated with the release of potential toxicants, such as metals. As such, chronic marine SSDs have already been established for some metals, including Ni. DeForest et al. (2013) published the first SSD for chronic Ni toxicity to marine organisms and yielded an HC5 of 3.9 µg L⁻¹, demonstrating that some species are sensitive to even low Ni concentrations⁵⁸. However, application of the SSD in a regulatory context highlighted uncertainty regarding whether Ni sensitivity differs between temperate and tropical marine species. As was recommended in DeForest et al. (2013), highly sensitive tropical species were excluded from the SSD in establishing a chronic marine EQS for Ni in

temperate European waters^{58,81}. This possible discrepancy in region-specific sensitivity was further investigated by Gissi et al. (2020) through the construction of separate temperate and tropical SSDs for marine Ni toxicity, which was made possible through the inclusion of studies published subsequent to the initial marine Ni SSD⁸².

Building on Gissi et al. (2020), here we construct general (Figure 4), temperate (Figure 5), and tropical (Figure 6) SSDs for chronic marine Ni toxicity. However, some species' effect concentrations, which were based on suborganismal studies or extrapolated from acute mortality data, were excluded because whole-organism, chronic, sublethal endpoints are ideally used in establishing environmental quality standards when exposure cannot be assumed to be exclusively acute (Appendix D). These SSDs enable the comparison of temperate and tropical marine species sensitivity to Ni.

Figure 4. SSD for chronic Ni toxicity to marine organisms

Species sensitivity distribution (SSD) including both temperate and tropical marine species. The derived HC5 of 3.7 µg L⁻¹ Ni is indicated in red. The gray ribbon indicates the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 5. SSD for chronic Ni toxicity to temperate marine organisms

Species sensitivity distribution (SSD) including only species found in temperate environments. The derived HC5 of 4.9 µg L⁻¹ Ni is indicated in red. The gray ribbon indicates the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 6. SSD for chronic Ni toxicity to tropical marine organisms

Species sensitivity distribution (SSD) including only species found in tropical environments. The derived HC5 of 2.1 µg L⁻¹ Ni is indicated in red. The gray ribbon indicates the 95% confidence interval.

The general SSD constructed here, conceptually equivalent to the SSD presented in Deforest and Schlekot (2013) but incorporating more recent toxicity studies, is in good agreement with the original study. Here, the general SSD produced an HC5 of 3.7 µg L⁻¹, which is highly comparable to the HC5 of 3.9 µg L⁻¹ derived in DeForest and Schlekot (2013). The HC5 derived from the temperate SSD constructed here (4.9 µg L⁻¹) is higher than that of the general SSD, while the HC5 derived from the tropical SSD (2.1 µg L⁻¹) is lower. This suggests that, although criteria derived from the general SSD will be adequately protective of temperate communities, tropical species may be more sensitive to Ni and may warrant more rigorous safety thresholds to ensure a low risk of Ni toxicity.

Overall, this case study demonstrates the potential value of region-specific SSDs in producing more refined, protective safety thresholds, provided that sufficient data

are available to ensure an adequate range of taxa are included in region-specific SSDs. Regional discrepancies can have important implications for site selection and permitting. Where ecological context, such as a temperate versus tropical climate, may influence community sensitivity, project planners should consider selecting sites with less vulnerable communities. For example, as demonstrated here, tropical project sites may require project designs that result in lower predicted environmental Ni concentrations than those for temperate project sites in order for mCDR deployments to be conservatively deemed low risk. Where data availability allows, such region-specific chronic SSDs support more tailored risk assessment at a proposed project site.

6.4. Data Extrapolation to Further SSD Development

As previously mentioned, the development of a reliable SSD is always contingent on the availability of sufficiently broad, high-quality data. As such data limitation is likely to present a near-term hurdle in the development of marine SSDs for stressors for which an SSD does not currently exist, which includes many mCDR-relevant metals (Appendix A) and carbonate chemistry perturbations (Case Study 1). Similarly, data limitation may hinder the construction of context-specific SSDs for more tailored assessments (Case Study 2). To address the concern of data limitation in constructing SSDs, a number of extrapolation tools are available. Both chronic marine SSDs and SSDs which incorporate extrapolated data have been used to inform EQS^{58,60,83}. The conclusions drawn from extrapolated data will always be less certain than those drawn from observed, chronic observations from relevant species, which calls for the application of more conservative AF values. Overall, the extrapolation approaches should be considered a temporary, supplementary solution until research gaps can be addressed.

6.4.1. Acute to Chronic Extrapolation

When chronic toxicity data are lacking, one practical alternative is to extrapolate chronic species SSDs from acute SSDs, which are often more abundant⁸⁴. In addition to expanding data coverage when chronic studies are limited, the inclusion of acute data frequently allows a wider variety of endpoints to be incorporated into SSDs. Specifically, acute toxicity tests typically assess endpoints such as immobility or mortality, while chronic tests tend to emphasize endpoints such as growth and reproduction⁶³. Although acute studies are inherently unable to capture delayed or long-term effects, their inclusion in SSD construction via extrapolation may be considered to improve taxonomic breadth.

To extrapolate acute data to chronic toxicity, an Acute-to-Chronic Ratio (ACR) approach is often applied. ACRs are established empirically by comparing results from paired acute and chronic toxicity tests conducted on the same species and chemical under comparable experimental conditions. However, when no empirical ACR is available, a generic or estimated ACR must be applied. This approach is functionally similar to the application of an assessment factor (AF). A wide range of ACRs across species and chemicals has been documented in the scientific literature^{61,62}. The U.S. EPA has also established representative ACRs for major taxonomic groups and chemicals⁸⁵. Functionally comparable assessment factors, based on the duration of acute exposure, are provided under EU Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)¹².

While ACRs are valuable tools for expanding SSD coverage, it is important to recognize that extrapolation introduces uncertainty. As expected, empirically derived ACRs vary considerably across taxonomic and chemical groups. This variability reflects not only differences in physicochemical properties, but also in toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic processes, which often differ between acute and chronic exposures⁶³. As such, the use of ACRs offers a pragmatic means of expanding the

utility of acute data and building robust SSDs, but their application requires careful consideration of underlying variability and associated uncertainties.

6.4.2. Freshwater to Saltwater Extrapolation

Ideally, saltwater risk assessments should rely solely on ecologically relevant marine species. However, due to the limited availability of such data, saltwater assessments are frequently based on a combination of freshwater and marine organism data^{60,86,87}. ECHA guidance on environmental dose-response characterization recommends applying an AF of at least 10 when deriving PNECs from combined freshwater and saltwater SSDs. This application of an AF of 10 is justified only when the combined SSD meets high standards for chronicity and broad taxonomic representation; when taxonomic diversity is limited, a substantially higher AF is recommended¹².

In the absence of sufficient saltwater ecotoxicity data a number of freshwater SSDs have been extrapolated to predict sensitivity in saltwater environments^{88,89}. A comparison of acute SSDs for 104 chemicals across freshwater and saltwater species indicated that freshwater SSDs can provide reasonable approximations of saltwater SSDs for many chemicals, especially in screening-level assessments. For a given chemical, the acute HC5 values derived from freshwater and saltwater SSDs typically differed by less than a factor of 10, provided that each SSD included at least eight species⁸⁹. However, to extrapolate solely freshwater acute data to a marine chronic context, an AF of 10,000 is indicated¹². In cases where adequate chronic freshwater data is available, a factor of no less than 100 is recommended, so extrapolations from freshwater data alone are unlikely to be helpful in practice.

6.4.3. Quantitative Structure- Activity Relationship Models

Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models are computational tools that estimate the toxicity of a chemical or a combination of chemicals based on its molecular structure and physicochemical properties. In constructing an SSD, QSARs can be used to generate predicted effect concentrations, such as the LC50 or EC50,

for substances that lack adequate empirical data across the taxonomic range required for robust SSD construction

QSAR models are increasingly incorporated into regulatory risk assessments. Under the EU REACH regulation, QSARs are explicitly acknowledged as an acceptable method for fulfilling data requirements if they meet established criteria: a well-defined algorithm, a clear endpoint, a specified applicability domain, adequate goodness-of-fit and predictive power, and, where feasible, mechanistic interpretability⁹⁰. The US EPA uses QSARs in procedures such as pre-manufacture notification reviews for new chemicals under the Toxic Substances Control Act⁹¹. The OECD has also established a guidance document on the validation of QSAR models⁹². In support of this increased regulatory acceptance, several regulatory and scientific bodies have developed tools to aid in the appropriate application of QSARS. Such tools include the OECD QSAR Toolbox, developed in collaboration with ECHA, and the US EPA's Ecological Structure Activity Relationships (ECOSAR) Class Program^{93,94}.

QSARs are particularly well suited to early-stage risk assessments. When applied conservatively, they enable practitioners to screen potential hazards, prioritize compounds for further study, and identify data gaps that require targeted testing. While QSAR predictions should not replace empirical data in final hazard determinations, they provide a scientifically supported and cost-effective means of extending SSD development and supporting provisional risk evaluations where measured data are incomplete.

6.4.4. Interspecies Correlation Estimation Models

Interspecies Correlation Estimation (ICE) models are statistical models used to predict the sensitivity of one species to a chemical or environmental stressor based on the known sensitivity of other species⁹⁵. ICE models are grounded in the idea that sensitivity to toxicants are correlated across taxonomic groups, allowing researchers to fill data gaps without direct toxicity testing. ICE models have primarily seen

regulatory application in the United States. Indeed, the US EPA has developed a Web-ICE tool, which provides a framework for generating toxicity predictions between species pairs using regression-based approaches⁹⁶. ICE models have been applied in ERA to estimate toxicity values for species lacking direct data, particularly for threatened and endangered species. They have also been used to support the development of SSDs and to inform the derivation of hazardous concentration thresholds (e.g., HC5) for regulatory purposes^{63,97}.

ICE models have the potential to improve the robustness and relevance of SSDs in ERA, especially for region- or taxa-specific concerns. For example, many SSDs are built using data from widely studied species (e.g., temperate freshwater organisms), which may not reflect the sensitivity of species in tropical or marine ecosystems. ICE models can help address this by estimating toxicity values for understudied species and expanding the taxonomic and geographic coverage of SSDs^{63,97}. This could lead to more ecologically relevant environmental quality standards and better protection for sensitive species in diverse ecosystems. The potential to predict the sensitivity of additional species, for which no relevant data is available, makes ICE models excellent tools for bolstering SSDs where relevant datasets are limited. To ensure accurate and reliable predictions, ICE models used to develop SSDs should meet specific performance criteria set forth by the US EPA⁹⁶. These include acceptable ranges for mean squared error (MSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), slope, and confidence intervals. These thresholds help ensure that selected models are robust and associated with low uncertainty in their predictions.

6.5. Mixture Risk Assessment

Historically, ERA has focused on evaluating single chemicals in isolation, but growing recognition of real-world exposure scenarios has driven increased attention to mixture toxicity assessment. Two major strategies have emerged to address combined chemical effects: the whole-mixture approach and component-based approaches^{57,98}. In the context of OAE, a whole-mixture approach would consider a

feedstock holistically (as an example, the mineral olivine), while the component-based approach would assess the toxicity of individual constituents within the feedstock to predict their combined effect (e.g., Fe, Ni, Cr, and Co - the primary metals in olivine). Both methods offer advantages depending on the nature and complexity of the mixture. In component-based methods, combined effects are typically estimated using concentration addition (CA), a widely accepted and conservative approach that assumes chemicals contribute additively to overall toxicity based on their individual potencies^{57,98-100}. While simplified frameworks like CA cannot explicitly capture synergistic or antagonistic interactions between mixture components, such interactions are considered relatively rare, particularly for metals, and tend to occur at high concentrations or with specific chemical classes (e.g., certain pesticides)^{57,101}. For screening-level risk assessments, these CA-based methods are well-established and fit for purpose. This section presents standard component-based and whole-mixture approaches of immediate relevance to mCDR and briefly explores emerging approaches to mixture toxicity, which can guide long-term goals for data collection.

6.5.1. Risk Index Approach

The Risk Index (RI) approach is a simple and conservative approach to component-based mixture assessment and is therefore recommended as the first step in mixture assessment. As described in Section 6.1, single-chemical SSDs are used to derive a RQ for that chemical, with a RQ ≥ 1 indicating potential risk for that chemical. If an individual component of a mixture has a RQ ≥ 1 , there is no reason to proceed with a RI approach because risk is already indicated. If each component in a mixture has an RQ < 1 , all the RQs of the individual components are summed to arrive at an RI for the mixture. If the mixture RI ≥ 1 , then potential risk is indicated at that mixture concentration⁹⁸. Because the RI is based on RQs (derived from SSDs) this assesses risk for the range of species in the SSD and cannot be used to assess taxa-specific risk. Furthermore, an RI approach cannot be used to predict the degree of effects associated with a given concentration, only to indicate the

presence/absence of potential risk¹⁰². This approach is highly simplified, but very conservative; an RI <1 strongly indicates there is no risk at the predicted mixture concentration, and no further assessment is needed.

6.5.2. Toxic Units Approach

The Toxic Units (TU) approach represents a more detailed component-based approach than RI. While a TU approach is more rigorous than RI, the benefit to such an approach is that its predictions are more biologically interpretable and do not incorporate the same amount of uncertainty^{98,102}. A TU approach will never indicate potential risk when an RI approach does not, so it is best applied when an RI approach has already indicated potential risk or when a more detailed understanding of risk to a specific species is a priority. In a TU approach, each constituent stressor's contribution to mixture toxicity is expressed as a toxic unit, calculated as the ratio of the stressor's environmental concentration (e.g., PEC or MEC) to a corresponding species' effect concentration for the stressor (e.g., EC50). Summing the TUs across mixture components yields an estimate of total toxicity for that species⁹⁸. TU sum calculations must be conducted for each relevant species or taxonomic group individually. To use this approach to derive protective levels for a range of species, an AF is applied to the TU sum for the most sensitive species, yielding a conservative environmental threshold¹⁰².

6.5.3. Whole-Mixture Approach

Whole-mixture approaches to risk assessment treat a mixture as a single stressor, without distinguishing the effects of individual components⁹⁸. This approach is applied in regulatory assessment when not all components of the mixture are well-defined (e.g. some effluent exposures)⁵⁷. Using a whole-mixture approach, the potential toxicity of a particular mCDR feedstock can be assessed following the same SSD framework as would be used for any single chemical (Section 6.5.1). Despite the relative simplicity of a whole-mixture approach, a whole-mixture approach also poses

significant limitations. A whole-mixture approach cannot account for variation in feedstock composition (components or their ratios) and therefore cannot be reliably extrapolated to other feedstocks, sources or batches. The whole-mixture approach would therefore lead to high redundancy in experimental efforts. The whole-mixture approach can also fall short when components of a mixture may move through or persist in the environment differently⁵⁷, though thresholds derived from whole-mixture testing may be protective if the assessment is based on the maximum environmental concentration of each component. Given these limitations, measuring the individual components of a mixture is highly recommended when using a whole-mixture approach. Although the component data cannot be used in whole-mixture analysis, this will allow for data from these studies to be integrated into component-based approaches, which will eventually allow for less experimental redundancy⁵⁷.

6.5.4. Models for Constructing Mixture SSDs

A number of more advanced component-based approaches to mixture assessment have emerged in the ERA of chemicals such as metals and pesticides. While these approaches are unlikely to be feasible for OAE project planners to implement at present, they can serve as a roadmap for the development of more sophisticated tools in the future.

Mixture modeling methods can be applied to produce mixture SSDs. As with single-substance SSDs, mixture SSDs predict what fraction of species will be impacted by a given mixture concentration, enabling the derivation of endpoints such as the mixture HC5, which cannot be derived using a RI approach^{103,104}. Mixture models, such as CA, have been applied directly to single-chemical SSDs to predict mixture SSDs^{102,104}. Mixture models have also been used to predict mixture effects for a range of individual taxa, with a new mixture SSD subsequently being fit to these predictions^{105,106}. Although data-intensive, mixture SSD-based assessments enable the prediction of effects at the community level¹⁰². These approaches also yield

endpoints, analogous to regulatory endpoints derived from single-chemical SSDs, with clear ecological implications.

6.6. Key Takeaways: Screening-Level Risk Assessment

1

Species Sensitivity Distributions (SSDs) provide a standardized approach to community-level risk screening and identifying species that may require advanced risk assessment.

2

SSDs are fit to effect concentrations for individual species, which are estimated by fitting a dose-response curve (DRC) to experimental toxicity data. If the species included in an SSD are sufficiently taxonomically broad, the distribution is considered representative of sensitivities across taxa.

3

SSDs have widespread regulatory precedent and have already been established for several metals in marine environments. However, significant adaptation is required for their application to carbonate chemistry perturbations.

4

SSDs for particular regions or taxa can enable more tailored risk assessment where data availability allows.

5

Data limitation is a considerable challenge in establishing an SSD, and data extrapolation can be validly used to improve taxonomic coverage, provided that associated uncertainty is accounted for.

6

SSDs can be applied in single-stressor or mixture risk assessment, and the latter may be particularly appropriate for mineral-based OAE.

^aFor better-characterized stressors, SSDs may already be in place. Pre-existing SSDs may be utilized in screening-level risk assessment, but it is encouraged to seek out additional chronic toxicity data to include newer studies and increase taxonomic breadth.

^bA variety of factors are applied to address uncertainty in extrapolation (Section 6.4).

^cExamples include species sensitive at PEC, endangered species, and economically or culturally important species.

Figure 7. FEMM pathway for screening-level risk assessment

7. Advanced Risk Assessment

Screening-level risk assessment relies on the comparison of estimated PEC and PNEC values, with the primary goal of assessing the potential for community-level risk. Advanced risk assessment offers opportunities to refine these PEC and PNEC values with mechanistic models. Although mechanistic modeling approaches are generally more effort-intensive than the statistical modeling approaches proposed for screening-level risk assessment, these refinement steps may be worthwhile when exposure dynamics at a project site are not sufficiently well characterized or when a risk to a particular species warrants more tailored assessment.

7.1. Mechanistic Models

Mechanistic models in ERA describe the biological, chemical, and physical processes driving the response of organisms or ecosystems to environmental stressors. The process-based nature of mechanistic models distinguishes them from statistical models, such as SSDs, which are based on empirical correlations rather than underlying mechanisms. Mechanistic models rely on cause-effect relationships and system-specific parameters (e.g., binding and complexation constants, uptake and elimination rates, and tolerance distributions), allowing them to simulate time-dependent effects and predict organismal responses under novel conditions. Unlike statistical models, which describe patterns in observed data and are often more straightforward to implement in screening-level assessments, mechanistic models mathematically express the processes that lead to different outcomes. As such, mechanistic models enable extrapolation to untested species and conditions¹⁶. However, these models require particular data, which are not routinely recorded as part of standard toxicity tests, and they can be computationally intensive. Mechanistic models can address some of the inherent limitations in traditional, statistical approaches to ERA, such as static exposure assumptions and limited consideration of time-dependent damage dynamics^{107,108}. However, given the data-

and effort-intensive nature of mechanistic models, they are best employed in scenarios where traditional statistical screening has identified the potential for environmental risk.

Key mechanistic models relevant to mCDR risk assessment fall into two broad categories: those that refine exposure estimates and those that predict biological effects over time. These tools offer a more realistic and dynamic basis for assessing the long-term environmental risks associated with mCDR interventions. Importantly, mechanistic models can be applied as steps along a modular pathway, either individually or in sequence, enabling assessors to tailor the level of complexity to the specific needs of the assessment (Figure 12). Their process-based structure allows for an interconnected flow of inputs and outputs, in which observed data or the outputs of other models can serve as starting points for simulations or benchmarks for validating predictions. In this way, mechanistic models can refine, corroborate, or expand upon the findings of statistical screening approaches, offering a more nuanced understanding of ecological risk.

7.2. Refining Exposure Assessment

Exposure assessment characterizes the likely magnitude of stressor exposure in particular locations or for particular organisms. These characterizations can be refined through the incorporation of dynamics such as chemical speciation and time-variable exposure profiles. Refined exposure characterization is particularly important when working in ecologically sensitive areas, in regions with known species of concern, or when likely exposure patterns are uncertain or poorly constrained. In such contexts, predictive tools such as biotic ligand models (BLMs) and fate and transport models help establish a robust understanding of the anticipated exposure profile, laying the groundwork for downstream risk evaluation.

7.2.1. Dynamic Fate and Transport Models

Dynamic fate and transport models are critical tools in ERA, particularly for predicting how stressors (e.g. metals) disperse, persist, and transform in aquatic ecosystems over space and time. These models simulate both the physical movement of substances and their biogeochemical transformations across environmental compartments and time, generating spatially and temporally resolved exposure profiles.

Fate models focus on chemical processes that govern contaminant behavior, including sorption, volatilization, biodegradation, and redox transformations. Transport models, such as hydrodynamic and sediment transport models, simulate physical movement through advection, dispersion, and deposition^{109,110}. In ecotoxicology, dynamic fate and transport models provide a mechanistic understanding of time-varying stressor profiles, which is especially important when exposures fluctuate due to tides, weather, or episodic releases.

Examples of combined fate and transport models include, but are not limited to, the Water Quality Analysis Simulation Program (WASP) and AQUATOX. WASP is a widely applied water quality model that can simulate the dynamic fate and transport of contaminants, including trace metals and nutrients, across one-, two-, or three-dimensional aquatic systems. It can be linked to external hydrodynamic and watershed models and includes sediment diagenesis modules, enabling the simulation of benthic-pelagic exchange and long-term contaminant cycling^{111,112}. AQUATOX, by contrast, offers a more comprehensive ecosystem-based approach. In addition to modeling chemical fate, it includes both bioenergetics processes and an effect module that predicts direct and indirect effects across trophic levels¹¹³. While currently limited to nutrients and organic toxicants (and not suitable for metals), AQUATOX's integration of fate and ecological effects within a single applied model makes it noteworthy for potential future development for mCDR¹¹⁴.

In the context of mCDR, fate and transport models may be particularly valuable for estimating the spatial and temporal distribution of metals and changes to the carbonate system due to the prevalence of projects in dynamic coastal zones. Interannual and seasonal changes in hydrodynamic conditions as well as riverine and groundwater inputs can strongly influence localized exposure profiles. Outputs from these models, commonly PECs, can be compared to EQS thresholds, like those derived from SSDs, or passed into downstream biological effect models for further refinement.

7.2.2. Speciation Models

Speciation models predict how a chemical distributes among its different forms (species) in the environment, such as free ions, complexes, or precipitates, based on water chemistry conditions like pH, hardness, and dissolved organic carbon. In the case of metals, free ion activity is often used as a proxy for potential environmental toxicity. A number of speciation models, such as WHAM and Visual MINTEQ can support exposure characterization by estimating the speciation of metals under site-specific conditions^{115,116}. BLMs first calculate metal speciation, then add an additional layer of refinement by incorporating taxa-specific competition dynamics for binding at receptors on specific biological surfaces, such as gills or epithelial membranes¹¹⁷ (Figure 8). Using either measured or modeled water quality parameters, BLMs estimate the bioavailable fraction of metals to specific species or taxa.

Accounting for site-specific bioavailability allows for a more ecologically relevant estimate of exposure, avoiding overly conservative conclusions that might result from comparing total or dissolved metal concentrations to effect thresholds. These models are relatively simple to implement, making them attractive for early-stage refinement. In some cases, they may demonstrate that risk is negligible, conserving assessment resources and focusing further efforts on only scenarios which continue to suggest plausible risk.

Several regulatory frameworks have already adopted BLMs or other speciation models to refine metal toxicity thresholds based on site-specific conditions. The U.S. EPA incorporates BLMs into its Aquatic Life Criteria (ALC) for metals like copper under the Clean Water Act¹⁴. Similarly, the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) integrates bioavailability-based approaches using BLMs to derive EQS values for metals such as Cu, Zn, and Ni, ensuring consistent protection of aquatic ecosystems across member states¹⁵. Canada employs BLMs in the Canadian Water Quality Guidelines (CWQG) to set refined toxicity thresholds for various metals¹¹. Australia and New Zealand recommend accounting for metals speciation when establishing site-specific trigger values for metals in both freshwater and marine systems¹³.

With their considerable validation and wide regulatory acceptance, BLMs are a logical fit for risk assessment of mineral-based OAE projects, where feedstock dissolution may introduce metals into natural environments. BLMs could also help mCDR project planners more broadly anticipate how changes to local seawater carbonate chemistry (e.g., pH) may influence the bioavailability of metals already present at a proposed project site. However, a key challenge at present for mCDR lies in the limited availability and validation of BLMs for marine applications. Most existing BLMs were developed and validated using freshwater data, and few saltwater BLMs exist with comparable levels of validation. Copper is currently the best-validated metal for marine BLMs, with site-specific criteria adopted in the US, EU, and Australia¹²⁻¹⁴. While preliminary efforts have been made to develop a marine BLM for Ni, no version has yet achieved the validation needed for regulatory adoption¹⁸. The further development of BLMs as a tool for assessing metals bioavailability in marine systems would refine the ability of OAE projects to assess risk at proposed project sites, as the bioavailability of feedstock dissolution products will vary based on the site's water chemistry. Until marine BLMs for metals of concern in mCDR are established, conservative estimates based on dissolved metal concentrations, derived from direct monitoring or fate and transport models, should be used to protect marine ecosystems.

Figure 8. Summary of the biotic ligand model conceptual framework

Abiotic speciation dynamics and biotic processes at binding sites mediate the bioavailability of a stressor to an exposed organism. Adapted from Guidance Document No. 38 Technical Guidance for Implementing Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for Metals¹⁹.

7.2.3. Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic Models

Physiologically based toxicokinetic (PBTK) models simulate the movement of chemicals through an organism’s body by incorporating absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion processes. PBTK models explicitly represent real anatomical compartments, such as tissues and organs, and the physiological connections between them¹¹⁹. These models rely on species-specific physiological parameters, such as organ volumes, blood flow rates, and tissue-blood partition coefficients, to estimate time-dependent internal concentrations across organs and tissues¹¹⁹. They are particularly useful for evaluating substances that bioaccumulate, exhibit tissue-specific toxicity, or are subject to biotransformation processes that influence the timing and severity of toxic effects¹²⁰. As such, PBTK models are useful in providing mechanistic insight when observable biological insights do not appear to correlate tightly with external concentrations in time.

PBTK models can be developed for a specific species-chemical pairing or designed as generalizable frameworks, although the latter still require species- and chemical-specific parameterization¹²¹. Model parameterization involves compiling both substance-independent parameters, such as physiological traits of the organism, and substance-dependent parameters that describe the interaction between the chemical and biological compartments. Data sources used in model calibration may include in vivo studies, in vitro experiments, statistical inference from existing TK datasets, and computational methods such as quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models (Section 6.4.3)¹¹⁹.

While PBTK models are better established in human health risk assessment, they are increasingly being applied in ERA^{122,123}. The same benefits that have led to their wide acceptance in human health risk assessment, such as the ability to provide insights into bioaccumulation, also make PBTK models a valuable tool in ERA. PBTK models are specifically indicated in OECD test Guidelines for Bioaccumulation in Fish¹²⁴. A main obstacle to the wide use of these models in ERA is the limited availability of validated models for various species and chemicals of concern. However, several PBTK models have already been implemented for use in aquatic risk assessment, particularly for species such as fish and mollusks^{120,121}. The OECD has released guidance on the validation and documentation of such models, which specifically addresses their application in risk assessment¹²⁵.

PBTK models can enable the integration of additional datasets into ERA by connecting sub-organismal processes, observed in laboratory experiments, to external concentrations, like those observed in field studies¹²⁵. They can also be used to extrapolate between different routes of exposure, such as ambient exposure and ingestion, which may be relevant for mineral-based OAE¹²³. Because PBTK models explicitly predict the accumulation of chemicals in tissues, they are also highly applicable for food web modeling, where understanding tissue-specific accumulation is critical¹²⁶.

7.3. Refined Effect Predictions with TKTD Models

Mechanistic effect modeling predicts organism-level responses to chemical exposure by describing the magnitude and timing of effects under different exposure conditions. Within TKTD frameworks, these responses result from coupled toxicokinetic (TK) and toxicodynamic (TD) processes (Figure 9). The TK component describes chemical uptake, distribution, metabolism, and elimination and is generally implemented using abstract, compartment-based representations. Where tissue-specific exposure dynamics are relevant, a physiologically based toxicokinetic (PBTK) implementation may be used (Section 7.2.3). The toxicodynamic (TD) component of these models, on the other hand, focuses on how the chemical interacts with biological targets to cause damage, including the accumulation and potential repair of that damage. TKTD modeling is particularly valuable for scenarios involving time-variable exposures, where statistical approaches may oversimplify risk. By capturing internal toxicant dynamics and time-dependent biological responses, TKTD models improve realism and reduce reliance on assessment factors. These models can utilize the outputs of other models, such as fate and transport models or chemical speciation tools, as well as field measurements or hypothetical concentration profiles, to simulate realistic exposure scenarios and improve the ecological relevance of effect predictions.

TKTD models offer a critical extension to traditional ecotoxicological approaches, helping to extrapolate laboratory observations into effect predictions for realistic, time-varying exposure conditions^{16,108}. Examples of TKTD models include the General Unified Threshold Model of Survival (GUTS), which predicts mortality under time-varying exposure, and Dynamic Energy Budget (DEB) models that incorporate TKTD (DEB-TKTD), such as DEBkiss, which predict sub-lethal effects like growth and reproduction by simulating how energy is allocated within an organism under chemical stress¹²⁷⁻¹²⁹. These models are particularly valuable for assessing risks in environments with fluctuating contaminant concentrations, predicting chronic and

delayed effects, and extrapolating laboratory results to more complex conditions or across different exposure scenarios.

In mCDR, where chronic and time-variable exposures arise from changing oceanographic conditions, reactive surface area-dependent feedstock dissolution (for mineral-based approaches), and/or the pulsed release of alkaline feedstock from discharge pipes or other infrastructure, TKTD models can supplement traditional toxicity endpoints (such as ECxs or SSD-derived values) and extrapolate risks across a range of scenarios. The use of these models is well established in ecotoxicological research for stressors such as metals, including some metals relevant to OAE, and pesticides¹⁶ and is increasingly being incorporated into regulatory frameworks. As an example, the OECD is actively working to standardize and validate TKTD models for broader adoption⁹⁹.

Figure 9. Summary of the generalized TKTD framework

External stressor dynamics lead to internal damage dynamics, leading to observable effects. Adapted from the EFSA Scientific Opinion on the state of the art of Toxicokinetic-Toxicodynamic (TKTD) effect models for regulatory risk assessment of pesticides for aquatic organisms¹⁶. Commonly utilized examples of TK and TD models are provided under each component.

7.3.1. GUTS

GUTS is a mechanistic TKTD model used to predict organism survival under time-varying chemical exposures¹²⁸. In the EU, GUTS has been deemed ready for use in aquatic ERA by EFSA, with GUTS modeling proposed as a legitimate alternative to certain dose-response experiments¹⁶. Other regulatory bodies have also demonstrated interest in using GUTS models in ERA. A study funded by the German Federal Environmental Agency applied GUTS to predict outcomes of exposure to plant protection products in a variety of soil-climate scenarios¹³⁰. The Dutch Ministry of Agriculture has also provided financial support for the evaluation of GUTS in meeting the needs of “Tier-2C” assessment (time-variable exposures) for the exposure of a range of aquatic arthropods to the pesticide chlorpyrifos¹³¹. Furthermore, EFSA has put forward criteria for the validation of GUTS models in regulatory applications¹⁶. GUTS models must be validated using an independent pulsed exposure dataset. Validation is essential if the model will be used for regulatory purposes. In the absence of validation, TKTD models are useful for exploratory or screening-level assessments but cannot support regulatory decisions, such as the derivation of EQS.

A key factor contributing to GUTS' regulatory acceptance is the ability to quantify and propagate uncertainty. During model calibration, uncertainty in parameter estimates is typically expressed through confidence (or credible) intervals. This uncertainty may stem from measurement error in the calibration dataset or from inherent biological variability across individuals. While experimental error can be minimized through study design, biological variability is an unavoidable feature. GUTS, and TKTD models more broadly, offer a structured way to explicitly capture this variability. In GUTS, both parameter uncertainty and stochastic survival processes are propagated through the model and reflected in predicted outcomes¹⁶. A further benefit of GUTS is that an open-source, user-friendly interface for the calibration and validation of GUTS for ERA has already been implemented in the openGUTS software¹³².

7.3.2. DEB-TKTD

While GUTS is currently the most regulatory-ready TKTD model, other frameworks such as DEB-TKTD may offer complementary insights to GUTS, especially in assessing sublethal responses such as effects on growth, and reproduction. DEB-TKTD is based on dynamic energy budget theory and simulates how chemical stress influences physiological processes like maintenance, growth, and reproduction^{127,129}. While DEB-TKTD may eventually offer valuable insights into sublethal impacts of OAE, it currently lacks the standardization, documentation, and regulatory validation that GUTS has achieved.

7.3.3. Data Requirements for TKTD Models for mCDR

As TKTD models like GUTS continue to gain acceptance in regulatory frameworks, their efficient incorporation into mCDR risk assessments will depend on purposeful experimental design that yields time-resolved datasets. Data required for the calibration of TKTD models is similar to what is needed for derivation of traditional dose-response curves, with the additional requirement that effects be recorded at more than one timepoint^{16,128}. As mCDR scientists move forward with traditional toxicological testing, collecting effect observations at multiple timepoints is low-effort and low-cost but provides significant added value in facilitating the development of future TKTD models for mCDR.

7.3.4. Effect Modeling for Carbonate Chemistry Perturbations

To date, no mechanistic modeling approaches have been developed to assess the potential effects of localized carbonate chemistry perturbations in the context of mCDR. However, a mechanistic effect modeling approach has shown promise in predicting the biological effects of pH perturbations¹³³. As such, the development of mechanistic models that capture the toxicological effects of shifts in carbonate chemistry on marine organisms would substantially improve the capacity for environmental risk assessment (ERA) of mCDR. However, applying these tools in the

context of carbonate chemistry introduces significant data demands. The calibration of models that capture toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic processes requires time-resolved effect data across multiple exposure profiles. A distinct advantage of biologically-based mechanistic models, such as PBTK and DEB models, is that they incorporate species-specific parameters that are independent of the chemical stressor^{120,127}. These parameters, which describe fundamental biological traits such as organ volumes, metabolic rates, and growth dynamics, can be applied across multiple stressors. Because these parameters reflect baseline physiological processes in unstressed organisms, they have already been established for many species. As such, mechanistic modeling of carbonate chemistry perturbations need only express how these underlying processes are disrupted by the altered chemical environment.

7.3.5. Case Study 3: Advanced Assessment of a Real-World OAE Project

To date, a small number of OAE field trials have been conducted around the world. Here, we demonstrate the application of FEMM to a real-world mineral-based OAE field trial, specifically the application of olivine sand to an intertidal shoreline in New York, United States¹³⁴. Olivine is known to contain trace quantities of metals such as Ni, Cr, and Co (Appendix A) with Ni typically considered the metal of greatest potential concern⁵⁰. While this single-stressor assessment focuses on the metal of greatest concern, this Ni assessment could also be incorporated into a component-based mixture assessment (Section 5.5). In this case, the mCDR project resulted in water column Ni concentrations that never exceeded $0.82 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. According to the U.S. EPA, the chronic marine water column criteria has a Ni concentration threshold of $8.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ¹³⁵. As such, any resultant introduction of Ni into the water column as a result of olivine application was well within existing regulatory guidelines.

During the project, Ni concentrations were also measured in bottom water at the sediment-water interface, a region relevant for benthic organisms where average water column measurements may not adequately reflect risk. Bottom water Ni

concentrations from olivine-treated sites peaked about 60 days after olivine application at $6.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 11A). While this is below the EQS ($8.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), it exceeds the HC5 derived from the published general marine Ni SSD ($3.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)⁵⁸, as well as the HC5 derived from the temperate marine Ni SSD ($4.9 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; Case Study 2), suggesting some potential risk to sensitive taxa.

Using openGUTS software (Windows v1.2)¹³², a GUTS model was calibrated to survival data for *Americamysis intii*, a bottom-dwelling temperate mysid shrimp¹³⁶ (Appendix E). Crustaceans are a key base taxa for SSDs, with the U.S. EPA specifically requiring SSDs to include either a mysid or penaeid shrimp (Appendix B). Furthermore, of the species included in the temperate SSD (Case Study 2), *Americamysis* was the most sensitive genus relevant to the east coast of the United States. The dataset for *A. intii* included both acute and chronic survival data, beginning with neonates. The model was calibrated to observed survival across a range of Ni concentrations over time, capturing how lethal effects progress during exposure (Figure 10). No validation experiments were conducted; however, in real-world applications of FEMM, such a validation step may be warranted.

Figure 10. Predicted LC10 and LC50 values for Ni-exposed *A. intii* over time

LCx estimates are plotted with their 95% CIs, based on GUTS-RED-IT calibration to *A. intii* data (Appendix D)¹³⁶.

Using the calibrated model, simulations were run with the measured sediment-water interface seawater concentrations from the field trial, beginning at the time of olivine application and extending over the course of a year. The model predicted survival probabilities for mysids exposed to the dynamic concentrations observed at the sediment-water interface following olivine deployment. After the first weeks post-deployment, when measured dissolved Ni concentrations were highest, the measured Ni concentration was never seen to exceed the chronic lethal effect concentration (LCx) predicted by the model (Figure 11).

Over the time period of monitoring, the results predict no sustained effects on mysid survival at the measured exposure levels (Figure 11A). To reach a 10% reduction in

survival probability, the exposure profile would need to be more than seven times higher (Figure 11B); for a 50% reduction in survival, more than twelve times higher (Figure 11C).

Figure 11. Predicted *A. intii* survival probability over time for varying Ni exposure scenarios

Column headers indicate the multiplication factor (MF) applied, displaying survival predictions under (A) measured field concentrations (B) the measured profile with the multiplication factor required to predict a 10% effect, and (C) the measured profile with the multiplication factor required to predict a 50% effect. Predictions are based on GUTS-RED-IT calibration to *A. intii* data (Appendix D)¹³⁶.

Although the measured bottom water concentrations in this case were not predicted to pose a substantial risk to benthic organisms, this example highlights the

applicability of GUTS to dynamic exposure conditions that arise from OAE projects. Average water column concentrations may not adequately represent stressor levels experienced by a particular taxa species, as concentrations vary between environmental compartments and over time. Mechanistic modeling provides a more realistic and taxa-specific assessment than relying solely on regulatory surface water thresholds.

7.4. Future Directions for Mechanistic Modeling

Although mechanistic effect modeling has thus far been discussed primarily in the context of single-chemical assessment, one of its notable strengths is its adaptability to mixture assessment, an area where traditional methods face major limitations. Mechanistic models, including PBTK and TKTD frameworks, can address mixture toxicity by simulating the time-dependent behavior of multiple stressors across tissues or biological effect pathways. Unlike traditional mixture approaches such as CA models, mechanistic models can explicitly account for differences in uptake, elimination, target organ specificity, and recovery among mixture components. This allows for the simulation of nonlinear, synergistic, or antagonistic effects that may arise from cumulative internal burdens or complex exposure dynamics. For example, a TKTD model was able to successfully predict sublethal mixture effects in nematodes and uncovered a mechanistic explanation for observed antagonism, highlighting how these models can yield both accurate predictions and biological insight¹³⁷. Mechanistic mixture assessments may be particularly valuable in the context of OAE, where feedstock composition and exposure dynamics may vary across mCDR technologies, project sites, and deployment strategies.

As ERA frameworks increasingly expand to address biodiversity and ecosystem-level effects, there is growing interest in extending mechanistic models beyond the individual organism to communities and populations¹³⁷⁻¹³⁹. Mechanistic effect models like DEB and GUTS have been integrated into matrix population models and individual-based models (IBMs) to capture broader ecological processes, including

reproduction, life-stage transitions, and intra and inter-species interactions. A DEB-IBM has been used to predict the effects of metal mixtures (Ni, Cu, and Zn) on a variety of biological endpoints for populations of *Daphnia magna*, including antagonistic effects at high concentrations¹⁴⁰. Further modeling efforts examined the toxicity of the same metal mixtures to a two-trophic-level community of various algae and daphnia species. This approach identified stronger community-level effects than would be predicted from single-metal assessments, likely due to indirect effects on food quantity and quality¹⁴¹. Incorporating community-level dynamics provides a more realistic appraisal of how stressor effects propagate through ecosystems. The regulatory use of IBMs and other population-modeling frameworks has so far been limited. However, interest in their application and validation is growing in academic, industry, and regulatory contexts¹⁴²⁻¹⁴⁵. Continued development of community-level mechanistic models will help bridge the gap between standard toxicity tests, conducted at the organismal or sub-organismal level, and the core goal of ERA: protecting biological communities and ecosystem function in real-world contexts.

7.5. Key Takeaways: Advanced Risk Assessment

1

Mechanistic models simulate cause-effect processes that drive risk, enabling refined exposure and effect predictions that incorporate, site-, species-, and time-dependent dynamics, allowing for more realistic advanced risk assessment.

2

Advanced risk assessment may be justified when screening-level approaches cannot establish low risk, with community-level assessments being refined through improved exposure characterization and species-specific assessments being refined through improved characterization of exposure and/or species sensitivity.

3

Where possible, mCDR experimental design should incorporate measurements of relevant water chemistry parameters and biological responses over time to support the development of mechanistic modeling approaches.

4

The further development of mechanistic modeling approaches can increase the capacity to predict outcomes across a range of exposure scenarios.

Figure 12. FEMM pathway for advanced risk assessment

8. Summary and Future Research Priorities

The Framework for Ecotoxicological Modeling of mCDR (FEMM) provides a tiered and modular structure for assessing ecotoxicological risk and other exposure-mediated risks associated with mCDR approaches that alter seawater chemistry or induce novel chemical exposures. It integrates traditional statistical tools, such as SSDs, with mechanistic models that simulate exposure and biological response under dynamic environmental conditions. This design enables FEMM to support both early-stage screening and more refined assessment depending on data availability and risk complexity.

FEMM emphasizes flexibility and scalability: SSDs enable transparent screening-level evaluations based on standard ecotoxicity data, while models such as fate and transport models, BLMs, PBTK, and TKTD approaches allow for increasing levels of refinement where project-specific concerns or complex stressor profiles demand greater realism. This layered approach addresses fundamental concerns in ERA for mCDR projects, where exposures are inherently complex and dynamic.

To advance FEMM's application and utility, the below research areas are recommended for development. Immediate research priorities focus on building the traditional, ecotoxicological datasets needed to enable ERA of mCDR-specific stressors, followed by the development of simpler statistical and mechanistic ERA approaches (e.g. SSDs, BLMs, and GUTS), with existing widespread adoption, to those mCDR-specific stressors. Long-term research priorities focus on the development of more complex or novel mechanistic modeling ERA approaches to mCDR-specific stressors.

Immediate Research Priorities

- 1) Generate chronic marine toxicity data for mCDR-relevant metals (Appendix A) that lack existing toxicity data, or for which available datasets have insufficient taxonomic coverage to support SSD construction (Appendix B). (Although often not mandated by standard testing protocols, studies should record water chemistry parameters, internal stressor concentrations, and biological effects across multiple time points to support mechanistic exposure and effect modeling).
- 2) Construct chronic marine SSDs for mCDR-relevant metals where they are currently lacking or use data extrapolation to compensate for incomplete toxicity datasets.
- 3) Generate chronic marine toxicity data for mCDR-relevant carbonate system perturbations. Consistent use of standardized experimental protocols (such as OECD guidelines) will improve comparability of observed effects.
- 4) Adapt statistical tools (e.g. SSDs) for risk assessment of carbonate chemistry perturbations.
- 5) Advance marine BLMs for mCDR-relevant metals to enable bioavailability corrections and support more realistic estimation of environmental exposure.
- 6) Advance GUTS for mCDR-relevant metals to facilitate predictions of survival effects under time-varying exposure conditions, which are likely for mCDR projects due to factors such as dynamic oceanographic conditions.

Long-Term Research Priorities

- 1) Further mixture assessment modeling tools, such as mixture SSDs, to account for complex interaction of trace metals, carbonate chemistry, and other co-occurring stressors associated with mCDR.

- 2) Expand mechanistic effect models for mCDR-relevant metals to include additional TKTD models, such as DEB, to enable the prediction of sublethal exposure effects, which may impact important ecosystem dynamics.
- 3) Develop mechanistic effect models, comparable to existing toxicant TKTD models, for carbonate chemistry perturbations. These models should aim to simulate physiological tipping points, recovery dynamics, and species-specific responses to fluctuating carbonate chemistry parameters.
- 4) Expand mechanistic extrapolation to higher levels of biological organization, such as populations and communities, by implementing TKTD models in an IBM framework.

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Glossary of Acronyms and Terms

ACR – Acute-to-Chronic Ratio

Ratio used to estimate chronic toxicity from acute data.

AF – Assessment Factor

A numerical safety factor applied to a toxicity threshold (e.g., HC5) to derive conservative regulatory limits

AQUATOX – Aquatic Toxicity Simulation Program

A fate, transport, and ecological risk model developed by the US EPA.

BLM – Biotic Ligand Model

Mechanistic model estimating metal bioavailability and toxicity based on site-specific water chemistry.

CA – Concentration Addition

Method to estimate mixture toxicity assuming additive effects of chemicals.

CCME – Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment

Sets national environmental quality guidelines, including CWQG.

CDR – Carbon Dioxide Removal

Methods for removing CO₂ from the atmosphere.

CWQG – Canadian Water Quality Guidelines

National criteria for protecting water quality.

DEB – Dynamic Energy Budget

Framework modeling energy allocation in organisms under stress.

DEB-TKTD – DEB-based Toxicokinetic-Toxicodynamic

Combines DEB theory with TKTD modeling for time-variable toxicity.

DIC – Dissolved Inorganic Carbon

Carbon present in seawater, important in carbonate chemistry.

ECx – (Effect Concentration x%)

The concentration that causes an x% effect on a specific endpoint (e.g., 10% reduction in growth or reproduction).

ECHA – European Chemicals Agency

Implements EU chemical legislation including REACH and SSD guidance.

ECOSAR – Ecological Structure Activity Relationships

EPA software that predicts toxicity using chemical structure.

EFSA – European Food Safety Authority

Provides risk assessments on food and feed safety.

EQS – Environmental Quality Standards

Thresholds set to protect ecosystems, often based on SSD-derived HC5 values adjusted with AFs.

ERA – Environmental Risk Assessment

Evaluates likelihood and severity of adverse environmental effects from stressors.

GUTS – General Unified Threshold model for Survival

TKTD model predicting organism survival over time based on internal damage dynamics.

HCx – Hazard Concentration for x% of species

Statistical estimate of concentration causing adverse effects in x% of species. HC5 is widely used in regulations.

IBM – Individual-Based Model

Models simulating individuals to predict emergent population-level outcomes.

ICE – Interspecies Correlation Estimation Models

Estimate toxicity in untested species using regression between tested and untested species.

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

UN body assessing science related to climate change.

LCx – (Lethal Concentration x%)

The concentration of a chemical that results in lethality to x% of a test population over a specified exposure duration.

MEC – Measured Environmental Concentration

Observed contaminant concentration in the environment.

MINTEQ – Metal Speciation Model

Equilibrium model for estimating chemical speciation in natural waters.

MRV – Measurement, Reporting, and Verification

Framework to assess and document carbon removal effectiveness of CDR projects.

OAE – Ocean Alkalinity Enhancement

Marine CDR strategy increasing seawater alkalinity to enhance CO₂ uptake.

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

Publishes environmental testing guidelines including for ecotoxicology.

PBTK – Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic

Model describing absorption and distribution of toxicants based on physiology.

PEC – Predicted Environmental Concentration

Estimated environmental concentration used in risk assessment.

PNEC – Predicted No Effect Concentration

Threshold below which adverse effects are not expected, derived from SSDs and AFs.

QSAR – Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship

Predicts chemical toxicity from molecular structure.

REACH – Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

EU regulation overseeing chemical safety and environmental impact.

RI – Risk Index

Composite metric of risk used in some risk assessment frameworks.

RQ – Risk Quotient

PEC divided by PNEC. If $RQ > 1$, potential for ecological harm exists.

SSD – Species Sensitivity Distribution

Distribution of toxicity thresholds across species used to derive HCx values and PNECs.

TD – Toxicodynamic

Describes how internal concentrations cause effects in organisms.

TK – Toxicokinetic

Describes how chemicals enter, distribute, and are eliminated from organisms.

TKTD – Toxicokinetic-Toxicodynamic

Mechanistic models combining TK and TD for improved predictions under time-variable exposure.

TU – Toxic Unit

A normalized measure of chemical concentration relative to its toxicity.

US EPA – United States Environmental Protection Agency

US federal agency overseeing environmental protection, including water quality criteria.

WASP – Water Quality Analysis Simulation Program

EPA model for simulating contaminant fate and transport in water bodies.

WFD – Water Framework Directive

EU legislation requiring good chemical and ecological status in surface waters.

WHAM – Windermere Humic Aqueous Model

Used to simulate metal complexation with dissolved organic matter.

Appendix A: mCDR Feedstocks and Associated Metals

SI Table 1. Composition and associated trace elements of commonly proposed OAE feedstocks

Feedstock	Composition	Associated Trace Elements
Olivine	$(\text{Mg, Fe})_2\text{SiO}_4$	Co, Cr, Mn, Ni
Basalt	Plagioclase, pyroxene & olivine minerals (primarily)	Al, As, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, V, Zn
Steel slag	CaO, MgO, FeO, SiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , MnO	Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, V, Zn
Brucite	$\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$	Fe, Ni
Limestone	CaCO_3	Sr
Lime/Cement Kiln Dust	CaO, MgO, Al ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂ , CaCO ₃ , MgCO ₃	Cd, Cu, Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, Zn

Note: The composition and trace element content of feedstocks can vary substantially depending on sourcing.

Appendix B: Proposed Base Taxa for mCDR ERA

Regulatory acceptance of SSD-based EQS derivation requires adequate taxonomic diversity to ensure ecological representativeness. Specific taxonomic criteria vary between regulatory bodies but require the inclusion of key ecological groups.

The US EPA requires a minimum of 8 families be represented to derive EQS in saltwater¹⁴⁵. More specifically, these families must include:

- At least two families in phylum Chordata
- At least one family not in phylum Arthropoda or Chordata
- Either Mysidae or Penaeidae
- Three additional families not in Chordata (including the unused family in 3 above)
- Any other family (to meet 8 minimum total)

In the EU, the WFD and REACH present aligned criteria for taxonomic representation in SSDs¹⁴⁶. These criteria are formalized for freshwater but have also been extrapolated to saltwater contexts. These criteria require the inclusion of a minimum of 10 species, although 15 or more is preferred. These species must include:

- A fish
- A second family in phylum Chordata
- Crustacean
- Insect
- Non-arthropod, non-chordate phylum
- A second insect order or any phylum not already represented

- Algae or Cyanobacteria
- Higher plants

Both frameworks emphasize the inclusion of fish, crustaceans, and primary producers in deriving EQS values. The selection of additional species to meet remaining requirements of taxonomic breadth is more flexible.

The following species and groups are recommended for consideration in mCDR-specific ERA based on ecological relevance, testing practicality, and sensitivity to key stressors. In selecting test organisms, the sensitivity of various life-stages should be considered. While data regarding the sensitivity of all life-stages can be useful, the most sensitive life-stage of an organism should generally be prioritized.

Fish

Sheepshead Minnow (Cyprinodon variegatus)

A standard marine test species with broad salinity tolerance and well-characterized sensitivity to metals like Ni. Useful for mCDR scenarios where metal bioavailability may change due to altered carbonate chemistry.

Crustaceans

Mysids

Sensitive to trace metals and widely used in saltwater toxicity tests (particularly *Americamysis bahia*). Relevant for assessing risks from mCDR-induced changes in metal speciation and bioavailability in coastal systems.

Copepods (e.g., Acartia tonsa, Tisbe battagliai)

Acartia tonsa is frequently used in pelagic toxicity assays due to its sensitivity to metals and ecological importance as a key grazer in marine food webs. *Tisbe battagliai* is commonly applied in sediment and porewater toxicity testing, making it

particularly useful for assessing benthic exposure pathways relevant to OAE materials.

Primary Producers

Green Algae

Non-calcifying algae that may benefit from added nutrients like Fe and Si released during OAE mineral dissolution. However, elevated concentrations of certain ions like calcium and magnesium may interfere with nutrient uptake and affect growth. Their response helps evaluate potential shifts in primary productivity from OAE.

Diatoms

Silica-requiring algae likely to benefit from OAE mineral dissolution products such as Si, Fe, and Ni. Their productivity may increase under OAE, especially in nutrient-limited systems, potentially shifting community composition and altering food web structure.

Bivalves (suggested taxa)

Calcifying organisms that are sensitive to both elevated alkalinity and trace metals. As filter feeders, they readily accumulate contaminants from the water column and sediment, leading to potential bioaccumulation. This makes them effective bioindicators of exposure and physiological stress. Useful for detecting impacts on shell formation and organism health in coastal environments affected by mCDR.

Annelids (suggested taxa)

Surface and sub-surface deposit feeders that interact closely with sediments. Some species, such as *Capitella capitata*, are known as pioneering species that rapidly colonize disturbed habitats. Relevant for assessing benthic exposure to metals like Ni that may accumulate following OAE mineral deployment.

Echinoderms (suggested taxa)

Developmentally sensitive to trace metals, especially Ni (particularly *Diadema antillarum*). Their early life stages provide insight into sublethal and developmental risks associated with mineral-based OAE inputs. Their embryos and larvae are commonly used in developmental toxicity tests.

Appendix C: Supporting Information for Case Study 1

This appendix presents the dataset used to construct the SSDs presented in Case Study 1: A Proof-of-Concept pH SSD. Data were compiled from several multi-species synthesis publications^{8,62,70}. Only species that exhibited negative effects in higher-pH treatments were included in the present analysis. A log-logistic dose-response curve was fitted to observed responses for each species to derive an EC10 (SI Table 1, SI Figure 1- SI Figure 13). If a 50% effect or greater was observed for a given species, an estimate of the EC50 was also derived (SI Table 1). The EC10 estimates derived were then used to fit an SSD for increasing. For many species included in this proof-of-concept case study, inadequate partial effect concentrations were observed for DRC-fitting to be considered reliable. Due to this limitation, as well as other limitations explored in Case Study 1, the ECx estimates and the subsequently derived SSD should be considered as exploratory and are not suitable for use in a risk-assessment context.

SI Table 2. Species effect concentration (ECx) values used to fit the SSDs in Case Study 1: A Proof-of-Concept pH SSD

Where possible, ECx values are presented with the corresponding 90% confidence interval (CI). In this context, CIs describe uncertainty in the exposure level at which a given effect occurs and are not reported when the ECx value could not be reliably estimated from the available data.

Species	Group	EC10 (90% CI)	EC50 (90% CI)	Source Study
<i>Neogoniolithon</i> sp.	Algae	0.02 (-)	0.05 (-)	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Ammonia</i> sp.	Foraminifera	0.06 (-)	-	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Heterocapsa triquetra</i>	Algae	0.08 (-)	0.50 (-)	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Homarus americanus</i>	Crustacean	0.09 (-)	-	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Prorocentrum minimum</i>	Algae	0.10 (-)	0.57 (-)	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Operculina ammonoides</i>	Foraminifera	0.16 (0.07- 0.24)	0.23 (0.18- 0.28)	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Marginopora vertebralis</i>	Foraminifera	0.30 (-)	-	Bednaršek et al. 2025
<i>Thalassiosira rotula</i>	Algae	0.52 (0.38- 0.66)	0.80 (0.74- 0.86)	Ferderer et al. 2025
<i>Atractoscion nobilis</i>	Fish	0.67 (0.46- 0.88)	-	Wittman and Pörtner et al. 2013
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> sp.	Algae	0.70 (0.60- 0.81)	0.88 (0.83- 0.92)	Ferderer et al. 2025
<i>Thalassionema nitzschioides</i>	Algae	0.97 (0.93- 1.02)	1.18 (1.14- 1.22)	Ferderer et al. 2025
<i>Chaetoceros affinis</i>	Algae	1.05 (1.00- 1.10)	1.14 (1.12- 1.17)	Ferderer et al. 2025
<i>Melosira lineata</i>	Algae	1.41 (1.32- 1.50)	1.82 (1.63- 2.00)	Ferderer et al. 2025

SI Figure 1. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of red algae in the genus *Neogoniolithon* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 2. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of foraminifera in the genus *Ammonia* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 3. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the dinoflagellate *H. triquetra* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 4. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the crustacean *H. americanus* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 5. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the dinoflagellate *P. minimum* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 6. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the foraminifera *O. ammonoides* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 7. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the foraminifera *M. vertebralis* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁸, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 8. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the diatom *T. rotula* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 9. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the fish *A. nobilis* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁶², and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 10. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of diatoms in the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 11. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the diatom *T. nitzschoides* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 12. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the diatom *C. affinis* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

SI Figure 13. Exploratory dose-response curve for the sensitivity of the diatom *M. lineata* to increasing pH

Where $\Delta\text{pH} = 0$ is defined as the pH treatment where the highest mean growth rate was observed within the study, and all other ΔpH values represent relative deviations from that treatment level. Experimental data are represented as blue points⁷⁰, and the fitted model is represented by the grey line. The grey shaded region represents the 90% CI and indicates uncertainty in the predicted response at a given exposure level.

Appendix D: Supporting Information for Case Study 2

This appendix presents the dataset used to construct the SSDs presented in Case Study 2: Comparison of General vs. Region-Specific SSDs. In order to construct general, temperate and tropical SSDs for chronic Ni toxicity to marine organisms, a combined dataset was created from effect concentrations, primarily EC10s, reported in DeForest and Schlekot (2013) and Gissi et al. (2020)^{58,82}. All reported effect concentrations (SI Table 2) were used to fit the general Ni SSD. The temperate and tropical SSDs were using species found in temperate or tropical regions, respectively. Species designated as “variable”, which can be found in both temperate and tropical environments, were included in the general, temperate, and tropical SSDs. For species with reported EC10 values for multiple endpoints, the most sensitive endpoint was selected. Where no reported EC10 was available, NOECs were included to increase taxonomic diversity.

SI Table 3. Species effect concentration (ECx) values used to fit the SSDs in Case Study 2: Comparison of General vs. Region-Specific SSDs

Species	Group	Temperate/ Tropical	Life Stage	Duration	Endpoint	ECx
<i>Diadema antillarum</i>	Echinoderm	Tropical	Embryo	40 hr	EC10 Development	2.9 ^a
<i>Acartia sinjiensis</i>	Crustacean	Tropical	Egg	80 hr	EC10 Development	5.5 ^b
<i>Hemicentrotus pulcherrimus</i>	Echinoderm	Temperate	Embryo	64 hr	LOEC Development	10 ^b
<i>Neanthes arenaceodentata</i>	Polychaete	Temperate	Juvenile	90 d	EC10 Reproduction	22.5 ^a
<i>Diadema savignyi</i>	Echinoderm	Tropical	Gametes	48 hr	NOEC Fertilization	22.5 ^b
<i>Tigriopus japonicus</i>	Crustacean	Variable	Nauplii	20-30d	EC10 Intrinsic Rate of Increase	29.1 ^b
<i>Monodonta labio</i>	Gastropod	Variable	Juvenile	30 d	EC10 Growth Rate	33.6 ^b
<i>Haliotis rufescens</i>	Gastropod	Temperate	Embryo	22 d	EC10 Metamorphosis	36.4 ^a
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Diatom	Variable		72 hr	EC10 Specific Growth Rate	122.7 ^a
<i>Americamysis intii</i>	Crustacean	Temperate	Juvenile	28 d	NOEC Growth	45.2 ^a

Species	Group	Temperate/ Tropical	Life Stage	Duration	Endpoint	ECx
<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	Echinoderm	Temperate	Embryo	72 hr	NOEC Development	89 ^a
<i>Americamysis bahia</i>	Crustacean	Variable	Juvenile	36 d	EC10 Reproduction	17 ^a
<i>Mytilus trossulus</i>	Bivalve	Temperate	Embryo	48 hr	EC10 Development	61.1 ^a
<i>Nassarius dorsatus</i>	Gastropod	Tropical	Larva	96 hr	EC10 Growth Rate	64 ^b
<i>Exaiptasia diaphana</i>	Cnidarian	Variable	Adult	28 d	EC10 Reproduction	65 ^b
<i>Amphibalanus amphitrite</i>	Crustacean	Tropical	Nauplii	96 hr	EC10 Metamorphosis	67 ^b
<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>	Brown Algae	Temperate	Zoospore	48 hr	EC10 Growth	96.7 ^a
<i>Champia parvula</i>	Red Algae	Temperate	Adult	10 d	EC10 Reproduction	144 ^a
<i>Dendraster excentricus</i>	Echinoderm	Temperate	Embryo	48 hr	EC10 Development	191 ^a
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	Bivalve	Temperate	Embryo	48 hr	EC10 Development	228 ^a
<i>Symbiodinium sp.</i>	Dinoflagellate	Tropical	-	72 hr	NOEC Growth Rate	310 ^b
<i>Tisochrysis lutea</i>	Haptophyte	Tropical	-	72 hr	EC10 Growth Rate	330 ^b

Species	Group	Temperate/ Tropical	Life Stage	Duration	Endpoint	ECx
<i>Strongylocentrotus purpuratus</i>	Echinoderm	Temperate	Embryo	48 hr	EC10 Development	335 ^a
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	Bivalve	Variable	Embryo	48 hr	EC10 Development	430.8 ^a
<i>Oryzias melastigma</i>	Fish	Tropical	Juvenile	21 d	LC10 Survival	1660 ^b
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i>	Diatom	Variable	-	72 hr	EC10 Growth Rate	2539 ^b
<i>Atherinops affinis</i>	Fish	Temperate	Embryo	40 d	EC10 Survival	3599 ^a
<i>Cyanobium sp.</i>	Cyanobacteria	Variable	-	72 hr	EC10 Growth Rate	3700 ^b
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	Green Algae	Variable	-	72 hr	EC10 Specific Growth Rate	17891 ^a
<i>Cyprinodon variegatus</i>	Fish	Variable	Larva	28 d	EC10 Growth	20760 ^a

^aEffect concentrations sourced from DeForest and Schlekat (2013)⁵⁸

^b Effect concentrations sourced from Gissi et al. (2020)⁸²

Appendix E: Supporting Information for Case Study 3

This appendix provides the complete output from the openGUTS v1.2 modeling software, which was used to fit General Unified Threshold models of Survival (GUTS) to laboratory survival data for mysid shrimp exposed to dissolved Ni¹³⁵. The calibration and predictions of the GUTS RED-IT model was selected for use in Case Study 2. This report includes model calibration settings, fitted parameter values, goodness-of-fit statistics, and prediction results. All content is presented as generated by the openGUTS software to ensure full transparency and traceability of the modeling approach used in this assessment.

Calibration

Calibration input data

Data set 1

File: Data edited manually

Description (optional):

Mysid 96 Hour

Control group: 'Control'

Survival data of input data set 1:

Time [d]	Control	18	32	56	100	180	320	560
0	41	40	40	40	39	40	40	40
4	39	40	36	37	35	14	8	0

Concentration data of input data set 1:

Time [d]	Control	18	32	56	100	180	320	560
0	4.3	17	28	46	80	150	250	350
2	4.8	19	29	48	84	150	260	450
4	4.5	19	30	49	84	150	260	460

Data set 2

File: Data edited manually

Description (optional):

Mysid Longterm

Control group: 'Control'

Survival data of input data set 2:

Time [d]	Control	5.6	10	18	32	56	100
0	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
28	67	66	49	57	64	50	6

Concentration data of input data set 2:

Time [d]	Control	5.6	10	18	32	56	100
0	4.5	9.1	11	15	26	37	62
7	4.5	9.7	12	20	32	49	84
14	4.9	9.3	14	20	33	52	93

21	4.7	12	13	20	32	54	92
28	4.7	10	13	20	33	52	87

Calibration settings

Calibration parameter settings for GUTS-RED-SD:

Parameter	Fit	Min	Max	Scale
kd	Yes	0.001641	143.8	Log
mw	Yes	0.001258	455.4	Norm
hb	No	0.00678	0.00678	Norm
bw	Yes	8.18E-6	741.5	Log
Fs	No	1	1	Norm

Calibration parameter settings for GUTS-RED-IT:

Parameter	Fit	Min	Max	Scale
kd	Yes	0.001641	6.068	Log
mw	Yes	0.001258	309.4	Log
hb	No	0.00678	0.00678	Norm
bw	No	Inf	Inf	Norm
Fs	Yes	1.05	20	Log

Note:

Background hazard (hb) was prefitted to control.

Calibration results

Fitted parameters for GUTS-RED-SD:

Best fit parameter values and their 95% CI

kd: 2.106 (0.5514 - 143.8*)
 mw: 46.34 (41.72 - 50.34)
 bw: 0.002358 (0.001693 - 0.003945)

* edge of 95% parameter CI has run into a boundary
 (this may also affect CIs of other parameters)

Goodness of fit for calibration data (GUTS-RED-SD):

Model efficiency (NSE, r-square): 0.9348
 Normalised root-means-square error (NRMSE): 14.44 %
 Minus log-likelihood (MLL): 402.47
 AIC: 810.94

Survival probability prediction error (SPPE) for each treatment:

Data set	Treatment	Value
1	Control	-2.2 %
1	18	2.676 %
1	32	-7.32 %
1	56	-4.03 %
1	100	15.52 %
1	180	-7.91 %
1	320	2.327 %
1	560	-4.44 %
2	Control	1.041 %
2	5.6	-0.21 %
2	10	-21.5 %
2	18	-11.5 %
2	32	-2.71 %
2	56	0.3973 %
2	100	0.9778 %

GUTS-RED-SD results table for LCx,t [[C]], with 95% CI:

Plots for GUTS-RED-SD calibration:

Time [d]	LC50	LC20	LC10
1	582.1 (325.1 - 1067)	237.9 (136.6 - 464.8)	149.6 (89.02 - 308.6)
2	250.9 (185.5 - 370.4)	119 (91.26 - 187.9)	84.7 (67.04 - 139.3)
3	170.1 (139.2 - 220.5)	89.71 (76.13 - 123.4)	68.73 (59.34 - 97.05)
4	134.7 (115.9 - 161.3)	76.98 (68.27 - 96.85)	61.91 (55.2 - 79.37)
7	93.73 (85.82 - 103.7)	62.43 (57.75 - 69.28)	54.3 (49.52 - 61.02)
10	78.63 (73.26 - 85.78)	57.17 (53.15 - 61.38)	51.63 (47.15 - 56.13)
14	68.96 (64.84 - 74.31)	53.85 (49.96 - 57.43)	49.98 (45.57 - 53.88)
21	61.14 (57.73 - 65.12)	51.21 (47.18 - 54.69)	48.68 (44.26 - 52.51)
27	57.75 (54.42 - 61.26)	50.08 (45.95 - 53.6)	48.13 (43.66 - 51.98)
28	57.33 (54 - 60.79)	49.94 (45.8 - 53.47)	48.06 (43.58 - 51.92)
42	53.58 (50.1 - 56.84)	48.7 (44.41 - 52.36)	47.46 (42.89 - 51.38)
50	52.4 (48.78 - 55.64)	48.31 (43.96 - 52.03)	47.28 (42.67 - 51.22)
100	49.33 (45.25 - 52.83)	47.31 (42.74 - 51.22)	46.8 (42.1 - 50.83)
182	47.97 (43.61 - 51.71)	46.87 (42.19 - 50.87)	46.59 (41.83 - 50.66)

Exposure, damage and survival plots for the calibration of GUTS-RED-SD:

... continued plot:

Observed vs. Predicted survival plot for the calibration of GUTS-RED-SD:

Observed vs. Predicted deaths plot for the calibration of GUTS-RED-SD:

LCx versus time with confidence intervals (plotted for 16 days, GUTS-RED-SD):

Fitted parameters for GUTS-RED-IT:

Best fit parameter values and their 95% CI

kd: 0.1316 (0.1026 - 0.1708)

mw: 59.46 (52.37 - 67.04)

Fs: 2.447 (1.989 - 3.297)

* edge of 95% parameter CI has run into a boundary
(this may also affect CIs of other parameters)

Goodness of fit for calibration data (GUTS-RED-IT):

Model efficiency (NSE, r-square): 0.9341

Normalised root-means-square error (NRMSE): 15.23 %

Minus log-likelihood (MLL): 403.09

AIC: 812.17

Survival probability prediction error (SPPE) for each treatment:

Data set	Treatment	Value
1	Control	-2.2 %
1	18	2.697 %
1	32	-7.19 %
1	56	-3.8 %
1	100	1.416 %
1	180	-10.5 %
1	320	11.53 %
1	560	-1.11 %
2	Control	1.043 %
2	5.6	-0.14 %
2	10	-21.3 %
2	18	-10.6 %
2	32	3.074 %
2	56	8.645 %
2	100	-6.8 %

GUTS-RED-IT results table for LC_{x,t} [[C]], with 95% CI:

Time [d]	LC50	LC20	LC10
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1	482.2 (402 - 565.9)	343.7 (271.2 - 415)	282 (211.4 - 349.5)
2	257 (217.6 - 297.8)	183.2 (146.4 - 218.5)	150.3 (114.1 - 184.6)
3	182.3 (156.6 - 208.8)	129.9 (105.2 - 153.3)	106.6 (81.78 - 129.8)
4	145.3 (126.5 - 164.5)	103.6 (84.73 - 120.9)	84.95 (65.68 - 103)
7	98.78 (88.74 - 109.4)	70.41 (58.86 - 80.95)	57.76 (45.47 - 69.11)
10	81.25 (74.24 - 88.64)	57.92 (48.92 - 65.88)	47.51 (37.79 - 56.23)
14	70.65 (64.85 - 76.65)	50.36 (42.83 - 56.97)	41.31 (33.01 - 48.38)
21	63.46 (57.7 - 69.92)	45.23 (38.25 - 51.44)	37.11 (29.58 - 43.7)
27	61.21 (55 - 68.28)	43.63 (36.66 - 49.93)	35.79 (28.43 - 42.39)
28	60.99 (54.7 - 68.14)	43.47 (36.5 - 49.8)	35.66 (28.31 - 42.27)
42	59.69 (52.68 - 67.47)	42.55 (35.45 - 49.11)	34.91 (27.6 - 41.7)
50	59.54 (52.33 - 67.41)	42.44 (35.29 - 49.04)	34.82 (27.5 - 41.65)
100	59.46 (52.08 - 67.39)	42.38 (35.15 - 49.01)	34.77 (27.44 - 41.63)
182	59.46 (52.08 - 67.39)	42.38 (35.15 - 49.01)	34.77 (27.43 - 41.63)

Plots for GUTS-RED-IT calibration:

Parameter space plot for the calibration of GUTS-RED-IT:

Exposure, damage and survival plots for the calibration of GUTS-RED-IT:

... continued plot:

Observed vs. Predicted survival plot for the calibration of GUTS-RED-IT:

Observed vs. Predicted deaths plot for the calibration of GUTS-RED-IT:

LCx versus time with confidence intervals (plotted for 16 days, GUTS-RED-IT):

Validation

No validation performed!

Predictions

Data set 1

File: Averages_0cm_Olivine_txt

GUTS-RED-SD results table for LPx [-]:

LPx	Value
LP10	9.263 (8.601 - 9.84)
LP50	12.57 (11.85 - 13.5)

Survival at the end of the profile versus multiplication factor for the exposure profile (GUTS-RED-SD):

Exposure, damage and survival plot for the predictions of GUTS-RED-SD (MF = multiplication factor):

GUTS-RED-IT results table for LPx [-]:

LPx	Best value (CI)
LP10	7.089 (5.657 - 8.336)
LP50	12.12 (11.05 - 13.27)

Survival at the end of the profile versus multiplication factor for the exposure profile (GUTS-RED-IT):

Exposure, damage and survival plot for the predictions of GUTS-RED-IT (MF = multiplication factor):

